

Chemical Reaction Optimization (CRO) for RNA Secondary Structure Prediction with Pseudoknots

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Abstract

RNA molecules play an important role in cell function especially including pseudoknots. Their functions are directly related to their secondary and tertiary structures. In past decades, there developed several methods to predict RNA secondary structure with pseudoknots, and the most popular one is using minimum free energy. The RNA pseudoknotted structure prediction is a nondeterministic polynomial-time hard (NP-hard) problem. We have proposed an approach based on a metaheuristic algorithm named Chemical Reaction Optimization (CRO) to solve the RNA pseudoknotted structure prediction problem. To solve the problem, CRO first finds all possible candidate stems. From these candidate stems, CRO generates an initial population. We have redesigned the reaction operators of CRO algorithm and used them on the generated population to find the structure with the minimum free energy. Four energy models have been applied to calculate the minimum free energy. Besides the basic reaction operators of CRO, an additional operator called Repair function has been developed here. Repair function has a great influence on our algorithm in increasing accuracy. It helps to increase the true positive base pairs while decreasing the false positive and false negative base pairs. To evaluate the performance, we have used five datasets containing RNA pseudoknotted sequences taken from RNA STRAND and Pseudobase++ database. Our algorithm has been compared with some existing algorithms such as Knotty, IPknot, Simulated Annealing (SA), and TT2NE. Experimental results present that our CRO based model is a better prediction method in terms of accuracy and speed compared to several competitive prediction methods.

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Chapter I

Background

1.1 Introduction

RNA is a vital biopolymer performing key functions of the cellular life consisting of four nucleotides: Adenine (A), Cytosine (C), Guanine (G) and Uracil (U). RNA structure is a construction of G-C, A-U, and G-U hydrogen bonds. They are called canonical pairs (generally base-base interactions) and are the main factors in the folding process of RNA [1]. There are three types of RNA such as Messenger RNA (mRNA) which carries genetic information from the nucleus to the cytoplasm of a cell, Transfer RNA (tRNA) that brings amino acids to ribosomes during translation and Ribosomal RNA (rRNA) co-operates with a set of proteins to form ribosomes. Besides the biological role of RNA in transcription and translation, RNA polymers have many significant roles in many cellular processes, such as carrying genetic information, taking part in the regulation of gene expression, functioning as catalysts in many biological pathways [1]. To understand the functions of RNA, we need to predict their structures. There are several physical methods to predict RNA structures like X-Ray, crystallography etc. These techniques are too expensive and extremely time-consuming [2].

RNA secondary structure prediction with pseudoknots is a significant challenge in Bioinformatics. RNA pseudoknots are found in almost all categories of RNAs [3]. Pseudoknots are formed when nucleotides of a hairpin loop join with a stem outside of the loop to form a helical stem that is adjacent or nearly adjacent to the hairpin stem. Pseudoknots have two kinds of loops—simple loops and complicated loops. In simple loops, there are nucleotides which are unpaired and in complicated loops, there are pseudoknot-free substructures such as several stems with their own hairpin, internal, and multi-branch loops. All the nucleotides in a pseudoknot loop (simple or complicated) are counted and the number equals the size of the loop. The unpaired nucleotides in these loops remain uncounted for calculating the size of a pseudoknot stem. There exist several proposed methods for RNA secondary structure prediction [2] [4] [5] [6] [7] and the most common one is using the minimum free energy method. Prediction of RNA structure including pseudoknots with minimum free energy (MFE) is an NP-complete problem [4] and it turns to NP-hard when the number of stacking pairs allowing pseudoknots is maximized. [8]. There have been developed many heuristic algorithms for solving this kind of problem [2]. It is believed that the prediction of RNA structure with pseudoknots is closely related to their 3D folding structure and the formation of the RNA structure is hierarchical, so predicting the secondary structure with pseudoknots can provide estimation on the 3D structure and the function of RNAs. Energy models for pseudoknots were studied elaborately in the previous years. It is proved that the additive model used in MFE folding can not predict the secondary structure with pseudoknots because it can not estimate pseudoknot energy [6]. Dynamic programming guarantees to find a structure with minimum free energy with respect to the underlying energy models [5] [6]. The studies based on dynamic

programming are limited to predict secondary structure without pseudoknots because it increases the complexity of both time and space. Rivas and Eddy [5] first introduced a method able to predict pseudoknots by the minimization of the free energy in polynomial time. They developed a recurrence relations containing a mechanism for generating pseudoknots. This algorithm has a polynomial complexity of $O(n^6)$, so it is difficult to use in practice. Dynamic programming approaches may not be applicable for longer sequences and the prediction results are poor. Heuristic approaches were developed as an alternative to DP due to its large computational complexity. Some heuristic approaches may output faulty or unreliable results, especially for longer sequences. Another problem is that the most heuristic studies employ the same energy model for pseudoknots as used in dynamic programming. However, the most successful models to predict RNA pseudoknots are based on the atomic coordinates of the RNA backbone [6]. Cao and Chen [9] developed a model (virtual bond model) based on polymer statistical mechanics to calculate loop entropy parameters for pseudoknots with interhelix loop of size 6 nt. The total calculation of partition function under the virtual bond model takes $O(n^6)$ time and $O(n^2)$ space.

In this paper, we have proposed a population-based approach, Chemical Reaction Optimization (CRO), for predicting the RNA structure including pseudoknots. Our main target is to predict the correct secondary structure with pseudoknots of RNA sequences. It is common that every molecule or ion that is not in the stable state wants to be stable by chemical reaction. The CRO algorithm follows this exact behavior. The important feature of CRO is its searching ability. It has both local and global search properties. High flexibility of designing reaction operators and population generation is another feature of CRO. These two features help CRO to fit for optimization problems and to find out the global best results of the optimization problem. In recent years, CRO has successfully solved many optimization problems and showed better results than other meta-heuristics approaches. Quadratic assignment problem, cognitive radio spectrum allocation problem, and network coding optimization [10], shortest common supersequence problem [11], protein structure prediction [12], and RNA structure prediction [13] were solved using CRO. The originality and contribution of the work are summarized below:

1. We have redesigned the basic four reaction operators of CRO to find the stable structures with minimum energy for both shorter and longer RNA pseudoknotted sequences.
2. A solution generation process to build pseudoknots has been introduced for generating valid solutions for RNA structure prediction problem with pseudoknots.
3. We have designed an additional Repair function which is one of our novel tasks. Repair function helps to generate more realistic and valid RNA pseudoknotted structure, while a solution is generated by any of the four basic operators of CRO. It has a great influence in increasing the accuracy of our proposed method.
4. Our proposed work follows Turner model, CC06, CC09, and LongPK models. CC06, CC09, and LongPK models have more developed energy parameters for calculating pseudoknot energy and to obtain minimum free energy than all other models.
5. These properties of the proposed work make it possible to give better results than other methods. The outcomes of the proposed work are compared with the previous IPknot [7], SA [14], and Knotty [15]. The proposed method gives output in the dot-parentheses format of pseudoknotted RNA structures. To depict the performance of our proposed method, we have showed the results in terms of Sensitivity, PPV, and F-measure.

1.2 Motivation

RNA has many significant roles in genetic and evolution process. It is also important for cellular life of our bodies. It is invaluable to predict RNA structures to create new drugs and understand genetic diseases [2]. Besides, pseudoknots are essential elements in RNA structure and almost all classes of RNA contain pseudoknots. Pseudoknots in RNA structure play significant roles in ribosomal frameshifting, splicing, rival genome replication, and regulation of translation [2]. RNA pseudoknot prediction is the basis of RNA tertiary structure prediction [3]. Prediction of RNA structure including pseudoknots helps the biologists to understand the mechanism and actions of the RNA pseudoknots in the cell. There have been developed several exact and heuristic algorithms to predict RNA pseudoknotted structure so far. The heuristic algorithms like GAKnot [2], DotKnot [6], IPknot [7] do not always predict the optimal structure and the accuracy decreases for long sequences of RNA. Yet, the exact algorithms take a large amount of time and memory. Chemical reaction optimization (CRO) is a newly invented metaheuristic for optimization that is influenced by the nature of chemical reactions. CRO is useful to solve various optimization problems. We are motivated to develop an adequate method to predict RNA structure with pseudoknots using CRO.

1.3 Problem Statement

The problem of RNA secondary structure prediction is, given an RNA sequence of length n , to compute its correct secondary structure. RNA secondary structure prediction is defined as an energy minimization problem, in which an optimal secondary structure (a secondary structure with minimum free energy) is to be computed. An RNA secondary structure is a collection of base-pairs. For all base-pairs in a secondary structure, if there exist two base-pairs (i, j) and (k, l) , such that they are not juxtaposed ($i < j < k < l$), nor nested ($i < k < l < j$), but they are overlapped ($i < k < j < l$), then the structure is called pseudoknot [2]. In RNA, pseudoknotted structures are formed by the crossing of base pairs. Pseudoknotted structures normally contain at least two stems such that the unpaired base in a loop of one stem pair with bases outside the loop to form another stem (Figure 1). Free bases are the volunteers in the formation of pseudoknots of RNA structure. Free bases of one loop pair with free bases of other loop using Watson-Crick A-U and G-C base pairs as well as Wobbles pair G-U [1]. Pseudoknot contains at least two stem-loop structures in which half of one stem is intercalated between the two halves of another stem. Pseudoknots are found in many RNAs such as viral RNAs, ribosomal RNAs, telomerase RNAs etc [16]. They play significant roles in ribosomal frameshifting, splicing, rival genome replication, and regulation of translation [2]. Pseudoknots are omnipresent and that are found in almost all classes of RNA and play significant roles in a variety of biological processes. We can better understand the RNA structure and their associated functionalities by detecting these vast class of RNA pseudoknots.

In our work, first, we have described the method to predict the secondary structure including pseudoknots from RNA primary structure which is a sequence of nucleotides. We find out a candidate set of secondary structure element, called pseudoknot. The final output is the structure which is more stable with lower energy among all structures produced by our method.

The length of loop L_2 determines which energy model is used for the respective pseudoknot candidate. For pseudoknots with a long interhelix loop (L_2), we employ a heuristic energy model LongPK [6].

For loop (L_2) length $0 nt \leq |L_2| \leq 1 nt$ and for $2 nt \leq |L_2| \leq 6 nt$ virtual bond model CC06 [10] and CC09 [19] are used respectively. For loop (L_2) length $7 nt \leq |L_2| \leq 50 nt$ a heuristic model LongPK is used. In above cases, stems S_1 and S_2 are regular stems. LongPK is also used for interrupted stems (S_1, S_2) of loop length $0 nt \leq |L_2| \leq 50 nt$.

We calculate the loop entropy for CC06 using equation (3) as follows:

$$T\Delta S(L_1, L_2, L_3) = T\Delta S(L_1) + T\Delta S(L_2) + \Delta G_{cs} + \Delta G_{assemble} \quad (3)$$

Where ΔG_{cs} is the free energy of the coaxial stack between the two helices and $\Delta G_{assemble}$ is 1.3 kcal/mol at $T = 37^\circ\text{C}$.

We use equation (4) for CC09 as follows:

$$T\Delta S(L_1, L_2, L_3) = a \log(l) + b \quad (4)$$

Where l is the loop length and a and b are fitted parameters for different loop sizes.

We use equation (4) for LongPK as follows:

$$T\Delta S(L_1, L_2, L_3) = \alpha + \beta \times L \quad (5)$$

Where L is the number of unpaired nucleotides in the three pseudoknot loops with different values of α and β . Here both α and β are heuristic energy parameters. α is the initial energy parameter and β is the penalty for loop L .

1.5 Objective of the Thesis

The major objectives of our thesis are as follows:

- To develop an algorithm based on the elementary reaction operators of Chemical Reaction Optimization (CRO).
- To design one or more repair operator(s) (if necessary).
- To determine the RNA structure with pseudoknots with minimum free energy.
- To calculate Sensitivity, PPV, and F-measure of the structure.
- To determine the performance of the proposed method by comparing Sensitivity, PPV, F-measure, and execution time.

1.6 Organization of the Report

There are six different chapters in this report. The content of each six chapter is shortly given below.

Chapter I (Background): This chapter is provided with an introduction about RNA, RNA pseudoknots, problem statement, and objective function of the RNA pseudoknotted structure prediction.

Chapter II (Literature Survey): This chapter contains the details and limitations of existing algorithms of RNA secondary structure prediction with and without pseudoknots.

Chapter III (Chemical Reaction Optimization for RNA structure prediction with pseudoknots): This chapter contains the details of how we implemented the proposed method by population generation, operator design, and operator selection.

Chapter IV (Experimental Results and Comparisons): In this chapter, we present an overall results of the proposed method and comparisons between the proposed method and existing methods.

Chapter V (Conclusions and Future Directions): This chapter presents conclusions and future directions.

Chapter II

Literature Survey

2.1 Introduction

In recent years, different approaches have been proposed to predict RNA secondary structure including pseudoknots. Some of them are briefly described here.

2.2 Exact Algorithm

An exact algorithm is an algorithm that solves a problem to optimality. Exact algorithms are designed in such a way that it is guaranteed that they will find the optimal solution in a finite amount of time. However, for NP-hard or global optimization problems, this "finite amount of time" may increase exponentially with respect to the dimensions of the problem.

2.2.1 Dynamic Programming

Dynamic Programming (DP) is a method of solving a complex problem by splitting up the problem into small problems. Then each small problem is solved and the results are stored and later they are calculated by the recursive algorithm. Based on this idea of Dynamic Programming (DP) several methods were developed to predict the RNA secondary structure. These methods used the thermodynamic principle of free energy minimization. According to the principle, the predicted secondary structure of an RNA sequence will have the lowest free energy. The studies based on DP are limited to predict secondary structure without including the pseudoknots, as it increases the complexity of both time and space. DP based algorithm, mfold [20], was developed by Zuker. One familiar limitation of the Zuker's algorithm is its incapability of predicting RNA pseudoknots. Addressing this problem Rivas and Eddy developed a dynamic programming algorithm for RNA structure prediction including pseudoknots [5]. The algorithm has a worst case complexity of $O(n^6)$ in time and $O(n^4)$ in storage. They have implemented a version of the algorithm that finds minimal energy RNA structures using the standard RNA secondary structure thermodynamic model. They have tested the algorithm on a group of 25 tRNAs selected at random from the Sprinzl tRNA database. The program finds no spurious pseudoknot for any of the tested sequences. A total of 63 pseudoknotted sequences of HIV-1-RT-ligand RNA, they have found 54 foldings that agreed exactly with the structures derived by comparative analysis. On viral RNA, their program predicts the 105 nucleotides downstream region exactly with $\Delta G = -32.5$ Kcal/mol. The major problem of the algorithm is the complete lack of thermodynamic information about pseudoknot

configurations. There is very little thermodynamic information available for regular multiloops, let alone for pseudoknots. The principal drawback is the time and memory constraints imposed by the computational complexity of the algorithm. This algorithm is not applicable for long RNA sequences.

Akutsu developed another algorithm [4] based on dynamic programming to predict the RNA secondary structure with pseudoknots. The most important contribution of this paper was that it corrected the previous misunderstanding that pseudoknots could not be handled by a simple dynamic programming-based approach. In that paper, a basic algorithm with $O(n^4)$ time complexity was developed for maximizing the number of base pairs where simple pseudoknots may appear. Then they applied a technique to develop an $O(n^{4-\delta})$ time approximation algorithm for most RNA sequences. The most important problem of their algorithm was that no established energy function was known for pseudoknots, especially for loop regions.

Lui et al. developed an algorithm (PreAlgorithm) [21] based on dynamic programming of $O(n^3)$ time and $O(n^2)$ space complexity. They considered several types of pseudoknots in RNA structure, and analyzed possible transitions between several types of pseudoknots. Their work was based on the principle of minimum free energy. In the algorithm, they used the thermodynamic parameters of M. Andronescu, A. Condon, and Mathews [22]. They proved that to search the maximum number of stacking base pairs there exists $1 + \epsilon$ ($\epsilon > 0$) polynomial time approximation scheme (PTAS). They presented a 2-approximation algorithm and analyzed the complexity of maximum number for stacking pairs of RNA structures. The algorithm divides the stem into several subsegments with a fixed length l . Then searches the optimal structure as the approximation structure of given sequence, formed by subsegments with the length less than the length l . They have simplified the RNA pseudoknotted structure with Basin Hoping Graph (BHG) [23]. They compared their algorithm (PreAlgorithm) with MWM, PKNOTS, and ILM algorithm and experimental results show that the algorithm outperforms those algorithms. They showed sensitivity and PPV as output. PreAlgorithm has an average of 91.8 PPV and 95.9 Sensitivity of predicting RNA pseudoknotted structure. They randomly chose RNA subsequences from the Rfam10.1 and PseudoBase as the dataset of their algorithm to compute pseudoknot. The advantage of the algorithm is that it can compute not only RNA pseudoknotted structure but also RNA-nested structure. The limitation of the algorithm is that the predicting accuracy of the algorithm decreases with the increase of the RNA base sequences.

Jabbari et al. developed an algorithm (Knotty) based on MFE to predict RNA structure [15]. It is a CCJ type algorithm with time and space complexity of $\Theta(n^5)$ and $\Theta(n^3+Z)$ respectively. While CCJ predicts RNA pseudoknotted secondary structures in $\Theta(n^5)$ time and $\Theta(n^4)$ space complexity. Knotty used HotKnots DP09 energy model [24]. Knotty breaks down an RNA structure into sequence fragments. DP matrices store minimum free energy of the sequence fragments. These fragments are used to drive the RNA structure. A set of grammar-rules describes the all possible decomposition of these fragments into smaller structures. The final structure is based on the DP matrix. Knotty used both pseudoknotted and pseudoknot-free datasets to analyze their performance. One dataset HK-PK-free is pseudoknot-free dataset which contains over 300 sequences. Other three datasets HK-PK, IP-pk168, and DK-pk16 contain 272 pseudoknotted RNA structure of length 26-400 nt. Knotty has the average F-measure of 76.9, 79.5, 74.0, and 76.2 on the datasets HK-PK-free, HK-PK, DK-pk16, and IP-pk168 respectively. Although Knotty gives efficient results in terms of Sensitivity, PPV and F-measure, the time and space complexity are

still much higher. For the sequence of length over 200 nt. it takes $1e+04$ MB memory and over $1e+04$ sec time.

2.3 Metaheuristic

Metaheuristic is a higher-level procedure or heuristic designed to find, generate, or select a heuristic that may provide a sufficiently good solution to an optimization problem, especially with incomplete or imperfect information or limited computation capacity. Metaheuristic is a high-level problem-independent algorithmic framework that provides a set of guidelines or strategies to develop heuristic optimization algorithms. Meta-heuristic methods are one of the common strategies for solving NP-hard optimization problems.

2.3.1 Genetic Algorithm

A famous metaheuristic algorithm called the genetic algorithm is a method for solving both constrained and unconstrained optimization problem that is based on natural selection. A genetic algorithm is usually used to produce ideal solutions for optimization and search problems by count on mutation, crossover, and selection. Tong proposed a method named GAKnot based on Genetic Algorithm [2]. In that paper, at first, they find out candidate stems, which are used to form the secondary structure. Then performed the genetic algorithm to find out the optimal solution with the lowest free energy. At first, a set of maximal stems was generated. Then several individuals were tried to generate by different combinations of stems. When the stopping criteria were met, GAKnot would output the best solution as the output of predicted secondary structure. Two different energy models were applied for evaluating the energies of stems as well as of secondary structures. In the candidate stems generation phase, they used the same energy function of Mfold [20] and RNAfold [25]. Then during the genetic algorithm phase, they adopted the D&P energy model with new parameters (DP09) by HotKnots 2.0 [24] as a fitness function to evaluate the fitness of each individual. They used two datasets for the validation of GAKnot. One dataset containing 41 sequences, is constructed from a subset of sequences used in HotKnots and another one contains pseudoknotted structures of RNA. The major advantages of their approach are that they released the restriction on the individual formation. They also did some modification on the operators and the format of the chromosome to improve the accuracy. GAKnot does not have a limitation on the number of iterations that the GA can run. They calculated Sensitivity and the Positive Predictive Value (PPV) to evaluate the attainment of the method. The major drawback is that the GAKnot algorithm cannot predict all secondary structures of RNA sequences with 100 accuracy because the fitness function, which is the energy function, is still imperfect. GA estimates certain energy parameters but it takes a long time for predicting RNA structure of sequences with a large number of helices.

2.3.2 Chemical Reaction Optimization (CRO)

Kabir et al. proposed an approach to solve the RNA Structure Prediction (RSP) problem based on a meta-heuristic algorithm Chemical Reaction Optimization (CRO) [13]. The target of the algorithm is to obtain a stable secondary structure with minimum free energy (MFE) from an RNA primary sequence. They developed the algorithm based on the helix to form the RNA secondary structure. They used the following equation to calculate the fitness of the RNA secondary structure.

$$\Delta G_{37}^{\circ} = \Delta G_{37}^{\circ}{}_{init} + \sum[\Delta G_{37}^{\circ}{}_{NN}] + \Delta G_{37}^{\circ}{}_{AU/GUend}(perAU/GUend) + \Delta G_{37}^{\circ}{}_{sym} \quad (6)$$

They used individual nearest-neighbor hydrogen bond model (INN-HB) to determine the energy of coaxial stacking base pairs. However, they did not work with pseudoknots, which is one of the major secondary structure elements [13]. Hence, there was no need for any loop length calculation or loop-bonding. For the experiment, twenty RNA sequences were taken from the RNA STRAND v2.0. The proposed method (CRO) was compared with the RNAPredict (GA) and the SARNAPredict (SA), COIN and TL-PSOfold method in terms of Sensitivity, PPV, F-measure, and INF. For shorter sequences (117nt. - 124nt.) the method gives the best output in terms of Sensitivity among the compared methods and the predicted best output is 97.3 Sensitivity and 100 PPV for the sequence H.marismortui (122nt.). For sequences (394nt. - 605nt.) the Sensitivity measurement is between 70 - 80 and for longer sequences, the performance is slightly decreasing.

2.4 Heuristic Methods

Heuristic method is a practical method of problem-solving that does not guarantee the result to be optimal but instead sufficient for reaching an immediate goal. Where finding an optimal solution is impossible or impractical, heuristic methods can be used to speed up the process of finding a near optimal or satisfactory solution. In RNA structure prediction, Heuristic methods do not necessarily return the MFE structure but they can include a wide class of pseudoknots and can use more advanced energy models with developed parameters in reasonable runtime.

2.4.1 Simulated Annealing

Kai et al. developed an algorithm based on simulated annealing to predict RNA secondary structure with pseudoknots [14]. They identified and maintained all possible maximum successive complementary base pairs. They randomly chose successive base pairs and thus generated new neighboring states. The schedule function of annealing algorithm was designed as to decrease temperature systematically and finally got the solution of RNA structure with minimum free energy. The performance of the algorithm was evaluated by the instances from PseudoBase database, and compared with IPknot [7], TT2NE [26], and CyloFold [27]. They showed the output in terms of Sensitivity and PPV. The algorithm has average Sensitivity and PPV of 92.6 and 84.3

respectively. By setting values of parameters and using modified evaluation function, the algorithm reduces the time cost to predict RNA secondary structure.

2.4.2 DotKnot Algorithm

DotKnot is a heuristic method for pseudoknot prediction that uses probability dot plot method to extract stem regions from the secondary structure and unites pseudoknot candidates in a formative fashion. The algorithm uses pseudoknot energy parameters from the virtual bond model [6] [19]. First, a partition function calculation is used for finding a set of secondary structure elements containing heuristically derived bulge loops, internal loops and multiloops with low free energy. This calculation takes $O(n^3)$ time and $O(n^2)$ space. Second, the algorithm assembles pseudoknot candidates and then evaluates pseudoknot energy using the loop entropy parameters [9] [19]. DotKnot predicts the structure of recursive H-type pseudoknots. Recursive pseudoknots are those where bulge or internal loops interrupts one of the pseudoknot stems. DotKnot constructs recursive H-type candidate pseudoknot in three steps. First, it unites core H-type pseudoknots. DotKnot evaluates free energy values for each core H-type pseudoknot by using the virtual bond models CC06 and CC09 for shorter interhelix loop lengths and the heuristic model (LongPK) is used for the longer loops. Second, it forms the recursive structure. Three candidate lists hold all possible secondary structure elements contained in each of the loops L1, L2, and L3 after examining the loops. DotKnot uses a standard MWIS calculation to predict the set of secondary structure elements with best local free energy for each loop. A recursive H-type pseudoknot is formed by combining the results. Effective loop lengths are used to evaluate the free energy for each recursive H-type pseudoknots. Finally and the third step, it validates the pseudoknot candidates in the sequence. For each pseudoknot in a sequence, DotKnot reports Sensitivity and Positive Predictive Value (PPV). DotKnot has been tested on different types of RNA sequences of both pseudoknotted and pseudoknot-free. DotKnot gives the best result in terms of Sensitivity and PPV for Escherichia coli tmRNA, Legionella pneumophila tmRNA, the SARS frameshifting pseudoknot, human telomerase, and Tetrahymena telomerase. DotKnot gives the most accurate predictions due to the improved energy parameters by Cao and Chen for the NeRV, and TMV3'-UTRs which both have five pseudoknots. Incorporating the energy models CC06 and CC09 for predicting simple H-type pseudoknots give better results than the heuristic pseudoknot energy parameters employed by the other algorithms. DotKnot is a more potential algorithm because it can predict pseudoknots with one interrupted stem. DotKnot is compared with different algorithms, namely pknots [5] and pknotsRG [28], KnotSeeker [29] and the heuristic approach HotKnots [30] for evaluating its performance. DotKnot gives the best Sensitivity and PPV value than others. The major limitation of the algorithm that it does not give the lowest free energy.

2.4.3 IPknot Algorithm

Another heuristic approach is using integer programming (IP) to find the maximum expected accuracy (MEA) of pseudoknots. IPknot [7] is a secondary structure prediction method based on MEA of the base pairs instead of MFE of a secondary structure. Sato et al. implemented the

program IPknot by utilizing the McCaskill model and the RNAalifold model in the Vienna RNA package to calculate base-pairing probabilities. They used the Boltzmann likelihood method to estimate the free energy parameters. They also implemented the Dirks–Pierce (D&P) model [24] that calculates the base-pairing probabilities. At first, IPKnot decomposes a pseudoknotted structure into a set of pseudoknot-free substructures and computes the base-pairing probabilities used in the IP objective function and next, it solves the IP problem to predict the optimal pseudoknotted RNA secondary structure. IPknot can predict a variety class of pseudoknotted structures. The threshold cut technique fits well with the idea of maximizing expected accuracy (MEA) and used in IP. Threshold cut technique and decomposition enable IPknot to perform quite fast predictions. They validated IPknot using three datasets (RS-pk388, pk168, Rfam-PK) of RNA sequences with pseudoknotted secondary structures. They have shown the comparison of time and performance between different algorithms such as ProbKnot, Flexstem, HotKnots, pknotsRG, ILM, NUPACK, and RNAfold. In fact, experimental results show that IPknot is more accurate than Iterative Loop Matching (ILM) and hxmatch on a dataset comprising sequence-based alignments rather than structural alignments. The main advantage is that IPknot can take either a single sequence or aligned sequences as input for predicting RNA secondary structures with pseudoknots. IPknot is fast and accurate enough for predicting both single sequence and comparative sequence analysis using a variety of structural datasets. IPknot produces much better predictions by heuristic refinement than that of without refinement. It should be also noticed that IPknot predicts more accurate on long RNA sequences, whereas its accuracy drops on short sequences, especially for IPknot without refinement, which is a major limitation of the algorithm.

Chapter III

Chemical Reaction Optimization for RNA Secondary Structure Prediction with Pseudoknots

3.1 Introduction

Optimization is one of the bases in science and many of the problems can be formulated in the form of optimization. An optimization problem can be defined as a problem of finding the optimal solution from all feasible solutions. Depending on the types of variables, there exist continuous and discrete types of optimization problems. Different optimization problems have been solved by different optimization techniques. However, there do not exist optimal solutions in polynomial time for nondeterministic polynomial-time hard (NP-hard) complexity class of problems [31]. The near-optimal (or sub-optimal) solutions are close enough to the optimal solution most of the time. Thus, there evolves a very influential class of optimization algorithm nowadays called approximate algorithm. In recent years, the field of Nature-inspired optimization techniques has grown extremely fast. These algorithms are usually general-purpose and population-based and are normally referred to as evolutionary algorithms because of motivated by biological evolution. Lam and Li [32] proposed a population based metaheuristic algorithm for optimization named Chemical reaction optimization (CRO) that is influenced by the nature of chemical reactions. The chemical reaction is a natural process of converting the unstable materials to the stable ones. In an atomic glimpse, a chemical reaction begins with some inconsistent molecules with enormous energy. The molecules collaborate with each other through some fundamental reactions and finally they are altered to those with the minimum energy to confirm their presence. When a molecule obtains excessive energy, it is unstable, and thus it manipulates itself to reduce excessive energy to stabilize itself. This process is called chemical reaction [33]. In the end, the molecule is converted to its' minimum energy to support its' existence. CRO holds this characteristic to solve the optimization problems. The molecular energy is of two types: kinetic energy (KE) and potential energy (PE). Potential energy is the fitness function value of the corresponding solution and kinetic energy refers to the tolerance of a system to accept a worse value. In buffer, there stores the energy of the surroundings. The principles of chemical reactions are governed by the first two laws of thermodynamics [33]. CRO follows the law of conservation of energy. In CRO, to maintain the law, the summation of potential, kinetic and buffer energy remains constant. CRO exchanges energy through reaction or search operators and thus CRO keeps the energy level constant. The second law regards the entropy of a system. Entropy is the degree of disorder and wants to increase. The system becomes disordered when potential energy increases and thus entropy increases. Then by releasing energy, the system wants to reach an equilibrium state whose potential energy decreases to a minimum. In CRO, to handle this condition, potential energy is converted to kinetic energy and also loses the energy of the chemical molecules to the surroundings.

There are three steps in execution of Chemical reaction optimization (CRO). They are initialization, iterations, and termination. In initialization stage, CRO generates population and initializes the parameters of the algorithm such as population size (*iniPopSize*), loss rate, collision rate (*CollRate*), energy buffer, kinetic energy (KE), decomposition threshold (α), and synthesis threshold (β) etc. In the iteration phase, the algorithm analyzes the solution space. The change of molecule from its unstable state to a stable state is generated by a collision and there exist two types of collisions such as unimolecular and inter-molecular collisions. Here, four types of elementary reactions occur. They are on-wall ineffective collision, decomposition, intermolecular ineffective collision, and synthesis. On-wall ineffective collision and decomposition are contained in the unimolecular reaction that defines the status when the molecule hits on some external elements like a wall of a container. The other two: inter-molecular ineffective collision and synthesis are contained in the inter-molecular collisions that define the collision between the molecules. A randomly generated number from 0 to 1 determines which of the elementary reactions will take place. If the number is greater than the collision rate, the intermolecular ineffective collision or synthesis will occur. Otherwise, decomposition or on-wall ineffective reaction will take place.

Table 1. Parameters used in CRO

Symbols	Algorithmic Definition
<i>PopSize</i>	The population size or the number of molecules in the population space.
<i>KELossRate</i>	The loss rate of kinetic energy in reaction.
<i>MoleColl</i>	The parameter which lies between 0 and 1 to make decision whether the reaction is unimolecular or intermolecular.
<i>InitialKE</i>	The initial kinetic energy is assigned 0 at the very beginning time.
α & β	They rule the intensification and diversification.
<i>Buffer</i>	Initial energy of the environment.
<i>NumHit</i>	Number of hit (<i>NumHit</i>) is a record of the total number of hits or collision of a molecule.
<i>MinHit</i>	Minimum number of hit (<i>MinHit</i>) is the number of hits when the molecule has minimum potential energy.
<i>MinStruct</i>	Minimum structure (<i>MinStruct</i>) is the structure of molecule with the lowest PE.
<i>MinPE</i>	When a molecule achieves <i>MinStruct</i> , <i>MinPE</i> is the corresponding PE.

The overview of CRO framework:

1. Initialization: Set parameter values to *PopSize*, *KELossRate*, *MoleColl*, *buffer*, *InitialKE*, α , and β . Initialize molecules with size equal to *PopSize*.
2. Iteration: For each molecule, assign a random solution to the molecular structure and calculate the Potential Energy (PE) by objective function. Until the stopping criteria not met, create the new solution using a reaction operator. The operator is chosen based on the decomposition criterion or synthesis criterion.

3. If there is sufficient energy to create the new solution, exchange the original solution with the new one and update the related kinetic energy (KE). Otherwise, continue with the original solution.
4. Final stage: Output the overall minimum solution, its objective function value, and corresponding results.

The advantages of the proposed algorithm (CRO) are as follows:

1. CRO can be applied to tackle problems in both the discrete and continuous domains.
2. CRO is a design framework which allows placing different operators to suit different problems.
3. Its variable population size allows the system to adapt to the problems automatically.
4. CRO is effective to tackle those problems which have not been successfully solved by other metaheuristics because of its' unique property of conversion of energy and transfer of energy in different entities and in different forms.
5. Incorporating other attributes easily into the agent (i.e. molecule) gives the flexibility to design different operators.
6. CRO enjoys the advantages of both SA and GA.
7. CRO can be easily programmed in the object-oriented programming language, where class and methods define molecule and the elementary reaction types respectively.
8. Parallelization of CRO can be done because there is no need for strong synchronization among the CROs during implementation.

3.2 Initialization and Population Generation

Initialization is the first stage of the CRO algorithm. In the initialization at first, we assign parameter values such as *PopSize*, *KELossRate*, *MoleColl*, *buffer*, *InitialKE*, two thresholds that are needed to solve our problem. To construct the population of molecules, possible candidate stems are found. The construction of candidate stems is easy. To represent an RNA secondary structure computationally, we use the same representation of maximal stem defined in FlexStem [34]. The construction of maximal stem is very simple: for a given RNA sequence with length L , we construct an $L \times L$ matrix (Mat). A particular row and column represent the corresponding nucleotide in the input RNA sequence. For example, row i and column j represent the i^{th} nucleotide and the j^{th} nucleotide. The value $\text{Mat}(i, j) = 1$ means an element in the matrix constitute a canonical Watson-Crick base pair (AU, GC) or Wobble base pair (GU), otherwise, $\text{Mat}(i, j) = 0$. We can find a list of maximal stems after the matrix is filled. Maximal stems are found by checking the 1s from bottom left to top right of the diagonals. Then we build a list of stems and in the list, each element stores the stem number, the start, the end, and the length of the stem. After that, by permuting the indices of the stem number of the list, we select randomly a sequence of numbers from the permutation which is said to be the randomly selected molecule. In Fig 2 (a), we put the value 1 in the square matrix, where the base pair is formed. Otherwise, we left it blank.

We take three consecutive 1's from the bottom left to the top right corner of the matrix as a single stem.

(a)

Stem no	Stem information		
	Start	End	Length
1	1	15	7
2	8	19	6
3	7	17	4
4	3	12	4

(b)

Stem list			
3	2	1	4
1	3	4	2
4	3	2	1
3	2	4	1
1	2	4	3

(c)

(d)

Fig. 2. (a) A sequence matrix in which the individual row and column represent the primary sequence, (b) Reported stem list with info of every stem consists of start, end, and length, (c) After permuting the stem number of the stem list, some values of the permutation are given, (d) Construction of pseudoknots from a randomly selected solution.

In Fig 2 (b) we have made the table of stem information where there are details (start, end, and length) of stems from the matrix. In Fig 2 (c) we have shown a permutation of stem number and

made a stem list. In Fig 2 (d) we have shown a solution from randomly permuted stems. The population generation algorithm is given in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1 Population Generation

```
1: Input: sequence, popSize
2: Output: molecule_list
3: for  $i \leftarrow 1$  to sequence_length do
4:   for  $j \leftarrow 1$  to  $i$  do
5:     if ( $j < i$ ) then
6:       if sequence[ $i$ ] and sequence[ $j$ ] makes a base pair then
7:         board[ $i$ ][ $j$ ]  $\leftarrow 1$ 
8:       else
9:         board [ $i$ ][ $j$ ]  $\leftarrow 0$ 
10:      end if
11:    end if
12:  end for
13: end for
14: for  $i \leftarrow$  sequence_length to 1 do
15:   for  $j \leftarrow 1$  to (sequence_length - 1) do
16:     if diagonal 1 found then
17:       information_table  $\leftarrow$  ( $i, j, \text{length}$ )
18:     end if
19:   end for
20: end for
21: for  $i \leftarrow 1$  to popSize do
22:   sequence_number  $\leftarrow$  randomly generate an array where each
23:   value is between 0 and information_table length.
24:   Add sequence number in the molecule_list
25: end for
```

3.3 Elementary Reaction Operators

We have reconstructed the operators corresponding to the four elementary reactions of CRO. After the initialization stage, a random number is generated to decide which operator will be triggered. The four reaction operators are given below.

3.3.1 On-wall ineffective collision

On-wall ineffective collision takes place when a molecule hits on the wall of a container. In this elementary reaction, there is a small change in the molecular structure and gives almost an identical solution. On-wall ineffective collision is used for neighborhood search. In Fig.4 m_2 is the newly generated molecule from m_1 after On-wall ineffective collision.

Fig. 3. On-wall ineffective collision

Two positions i and j in m_1 is randomly chosen. The value of j is added to the value in i^{th} position of m_1 and assigned to m_2 if the length of m_1 is less than or equals to the summation of the values in i^{th} and j^{th} positions. Otherwise, the randomly selected j^{th} value is added to m_2 . The other indices are assigned the values from the corresponding indices of m_1 . This change helps to find the neighbor solution on the spaces. The algorithm for On-wall ineffective collision is given in Algorithm 2.

Algorithm 2 On-Wall Ineffective Collision

```
1: Input:  $m_1[1, 2, \dots, n]$ 
2: Output:  $m_2$ 
3:  $m_2 \leftarrow m_1$ 
4: for  $i \leftarrow 0$  to 1 do
5:   Generate two random numbers  $i, j$  ranging from 0 to  $n$ 
6:   if  $(m_1[i] + j \leq \text{length}(m_1))$  then
7:      $m_2[i] \leftarrow (m_1[i] + j)$ 
8:   else
9:     if  $(m_1[i] > j)$  then
10:       $m_2[i] \leftarrow (m_1[i] - j)$ 
11:     else
12:       $m_2[i] \leftarrow (j - m_1[i])$ 
13:     end if
14:   end if
15: end for
```

3.3.2. Decomposition

In a decomposition, a molecule hits a wall and then breaks into several molecules. In this reaction there occur excessive changes in the molecular structures of the new molecules. Decomposition is used to analyze another area of the search space. This can be the situation when local search finishes and solution bounces to other portion of the solution space. In this way, a global search is performed.

Fig. 4. Decomposition

At first, m_1 breaks down into two equal parts. A new m_2 is generated by the first part of the m_1 and rest half is picked randomly. Similarly, m_3 is generated by the last part of the m_1 and rest half is picked randomly. Randomly produced part is created from random values within 0 to the length of m_1 . The reaction creates two molecules of different molecular structures from the initial molecule. The algorithm for decomposition is given in Algorithm 3.

Algorithm 3 Decomposition

- 1: **Input:** $m_1[1, 2, \dots, n]$
 - 2: **Output:** m_2, m_3
 - 3: $mid \leftarrow n/2$
 - 4: $m_2[1 : mid - 1] \leftarrow m_1[1 : mid - 1]$
 - 5: $m_3[mid - 1 : n] \leftarrow m_1[mid - 1 : n]$
 - 6: $m_2[0 : mid - 1] \leftarrow random(0 : n)$
 - 7: $m_3[mid - 1 : n] \leftarrow random(0 : n)$
-

3.3.3 Intermolecular Ineffective Collision

An intermolecular ineffective collision occurs when several molecules collide with each other and then bounce away. The number of molecules remains unchanged before and after the collision. The more energy in the subsystem and thus, the more flexibility for the molecules to modify their molecular structures is obtained by the more number of molecules involved in the subsystem. The intermolecular ineffective collision is applied to local search where the reactant molecules have minimal change in their molecular structure.

Fig. 5. Intermolecular ineffective collision

This reaction operator adopts two molecules m_1 and m_2 randomly from the population and produces two new molecules m_{11} and m_{21} . Two points have been generated randomly such that the two points divide both initial solutions into three parts. Then the one part of the m_1 and one part of the m_2 join up to form m_{11} and the other part of the m_1 and the other part of the m_2 join up to form m_{21} . The one-third portion of the molecular structure of the reactants is changed and the two-thirds remains unchanged. This exchange causes the build of the new solutions. The algorithm for Intermolecular ineffective collision is given in Algorithm 4.

Algorithm 4 Inter-molecular Ineffective Collision

```

1: Input:  $m_1[1, 2, \dots, n], m_2[1, 2, \dots, n]$ 
2: Output:  $m_{11}, m_{22}$ 
3:  $x \leftarrow \text{random}(0 : n)$ 
4:  $y \leftarrow \text{random}(0 : n)$ 
5: for  $i \leftarrow 1$  to  $n$  do
6:   if  $(i < x$  or  $i > y)$  then
7:      $m_{11}[i] \leftarrow m_1[i]$ 
8:      $m_{22}[i] \leftarrow m_2[i]$ 
9:   else if  $(x \leq i$  and  $i \leq y)$  then
10:     $m_{11}[i] \leftarrow m_2[i]$ 
11:     $m_{22}[i] \leftarrow m_1[i]$ 
12:   end if
13: end for

```

3.3.4 Synthesis

A synthesis refers to the situation when multiple molecules hit against each other and integrate together to form one new single molecule. This reaction acts opposite of decomposition.

Fig. 6. Synthesis

Two molecules m_1 and m_2 from the population are combined to form a new molecule m_3 in the synthesis reaction. This is the opposite of the decomposition reaction. Two molecules m_1 and m_2 are chosen randomly from the population in Fig. 5. The second step is to take a random value between 0 and 1. This random value helps to determine the molecule to choose. If the random value is less than 0.5, m_1 is chosen to select value. Otherwise, m_2 is chosen to select a value for m_3 . The reaction operators work according to the values of some parameters.

A random variable b is generated to decide either the reaction is unimolecular or intermolecular. If $b > \text{Molecol}$, then the reaction is unimolecular. Otherwise, intermolecular. If the reaction is unimolecular and satisfies the condition of decomposition, then the reaction is decomposition. Otherwise, it is an on-wall ineffective reaction. If the reaction is intermolecular and satisfies the condition of synthesis, then it is a synthesis. Otherwise, it is an intermolecular ineffective collision. The algorithm for Synthesis is given in Algorithm 5.

Algorithm 5 Synthesis

```

1: Input:  $m_1[1, 2, \dots, n], m_2[1, 2, \dots, n]$ 
2: Output:  $m_3$ 
3: for  $i \leftarrow 1$  to  $n$  do
4:    $r \leftarrow \text{random}(0 : 1)$ 
5:   if  $(r < 0.5)$  then
6:      $m_3[i] \leftarrow m_1[i]$ 
7:   else
8:      $m_3[i] \leftarrow m_2[i]$ 
9:   end if
10: end for

```

3.3.5 Repair Operator

A hairpin loop is an unpaired loop of messenger RNA that is created when an RNA strand folds and forms base pairs with another section of the same strand. The resulting structure looks like a loop or a U-shape. Hairpins are a common type of secondary structure in RNA molecules. Especially in mRNA, hairpin loops occur frequently [7].

Fig. 7. Hairpin loop

Repair function is applied after the basic reaction operator of CRO at each iteration. Stem information table is rechecked if the stem information contains a hairpin loop or not. If the value of $hp = (end - start - 2 \times length + 1)$ is greater than 0, then it contains a hairpin loop of length as the same value of hp . If any stem information does not contain any hairpin loop, then RepairHP() creates a hairpin loop by decreasing the length of stem by 1 or 2.

Input Sequence: GGGGUUCGAAUCCCCGGGGCCCA

Sl.	Start	End	Length		Sl.	Start	End	Length
1	0	13	7	→	1	0	13	6
2	1	21	6		2	1	21	6
3	11	18	4		3	11	18	4
4	16	21	3		4	16	21	3

Stem Information before RepairHP() Stem Information after RepairHP()

Index	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
Primary Sequence	G	G	G	G	U	U	C	G	A	A	U	C	C	C	C	G	G	G	G	C	C	C	A
Unrepaired structure	((((((()))))))
Repaired structure	(((((.	.	.	.)))))

Fig. 8. Constructing an RNA structure from stem information

Algorithm 6 Repair

```

1: Input:  $info\_table_1[1, 2, \dots, n]$ 
2: Output:  $info\_table_2[1, 2, \dots, n]$ 
3:  $info\_table_2 \leftarrow info\_table_1$ 
4: for  $i \leftarrow 1$  to  $n$  do
5:    $(start, end, length) \leftarrow info\_table_1[i]$ 
6:    $hp \leftarrow (end - start - 2 \times length + 1)$ 
7:   if  $(hp == 0)$  then
8:      $length \leftarrow length - 2$ 
9:   else if  $(hp == 1)$  then
10:     $length \leftarrow length - 1$ 
11:   end if
12:    $info\_table_2[i] \leftarrow (start, end, length)$ 
13: end for

```

From Fig. 8 we see that the stem (0, 13, 7) starts from index 0 and ends in index 13 with length 7. In our algorithm, after placing seven consecutive parentheses from both ends, if the parentheses from both sides make structure like this [(((((((.....)))))))]], we cut one or two base pairs to form loop. Then we have this structure folded as [((((.....)))))]]. So, placing parentheses in the

places of dots means more False Positives (FP). Repair operator removes the parentheses and puts dots in those indices, thus False Positives decrease and the accuracy increases. To preserve the natural property of RNA, we have designed the Repair operator called RepairHP(). The algorithm for RepairHP() is given in Algorithm 6.

3.4 Experimental Setup

In the proposed CRO algorithm for RNA structure prediction with pseudoknots, there are some key parameters. Our proposed method have been investigated for the best value by testing CRO on a subset on CC06 dataset containing 10 RNA sequences for which the results have been shown in Table 6. The tuning process is demonstrated in Fig. 9 (for α), Fig. 10 (for β), Fig. 11 (for *iteration*), and Fig. 12 (for *KELossRate*). In Fig. 9, a graph has been drawn to show the effect of the value of α over the value of F-measure (used in equation 9). Here α has been plotted in the x-axis and F-measure has been plotted in the y-axis. From the graph, it can be seen that the highest value (87.31) of F-measure is obtained for $\alpha = 1$. Similarly, from Fig. 10 we have got the highest value (89.80) of F-measure for $\beta = 8$. When we have fixed the value of $\alpha = 1$ and the value of $\beta = 8$, then the best output in terms of F-measure is found. In Fig. 11, it can be seen that, from iterations 50 to 80 the value of F-measure was improving and the highest value is found after 80 iterations. From 90 to 500 iterations, there was no significant change in F-measure. Finally, we have got the highest value at *KELossRate* = 0.55, showed in Fig. 12.

Fig. 9. Parameter tuning for α against F-measure

Fig. 10. Parameter tuning for β against F-measure

Fig. 11. Parameter tuning for *iteration* against F-measure

Fig. 12. Parameter tuning for *KELossRate* against F-measure

The performance of the CRO algorithm depends on the proper tuning of values of the parameters. *KELossRate*, *InitialKE*, *Molecoll*, *PopSize*, *NumHit*, *MinHit*, *MinStruct* etc. are some of the parameters. The output of our algorithm for RNA structure prediction with pseudoknots depends significantly on the appropriate values of these parameters. The combination of parameter values that we have used in our problem to maximize the performance is given in Table 2.

Table 2: Initial value of parameters of CRO for RNA structure prediction with pseudoknots.

Symbol	Value
<i>Iteration</i>	80
<i>PopSize</i>	50
<i>KELossRate</i>	.55
<i>MoleColl</i>	.35
<i>InitialKE</i>	0
<i>Alpha (α)</i>	1
<i>Beta (β)</i>	8
<i>Buffer</i>	0
<i>NumHit</i>	0
<i>MinHit</i>	0
<i>PE</i>	Equation 2 to 5

3.5 Operator selection

In this section, we have explained the operator selection process of the CRO algorithm. A flowchart in (Fig. 13) represents the stages of CRO execution step by step and also the operator selection procedure. The START and END denote the beginning and the finishing of CRO algorithm respectively. The algorithm starts with the stage initialization stage. In this stage, values are assigned to CRO parameters as well as some variables. The initial population of molecules are generated randomly based on our problem according to the value of the parameter PopSize. We search out some feasible solution from all generated solutions. Flowchart of operator selection of the proposed algorithm is shown in Fig. 13.

Fig. 13. Flowchart of operator selection

At the next stage, the iteration stage, a number of iterations are executed. There will be a collision and one of the operators will be triggered at each iteration. The collision that will occur depends on a random variable ranges 0 to 1. When there is only one molecule in the population or the random number is greater than the value of the parameter *MoleColl*, the unimolecular collision occurs. Otherwise, intermolecular collision takes place. At later step, the conditions of the decomposition and synthesis operators are inspected. The value of α is significant to select the operator whether it will be on-wall ineffective or decomposition. Similarly, the value of β , to select between intermolecular ineffective and synthesis. Then the solution is passed to the repair operator and the repair operator performs repair if necessary to make more accurate and stable structure. The iteration stage continues until it satisfies the termination condition. The termination condition may be defined by the maximum number of iterations performed or by a desired objective function value. In the final stage, the algorithm terminates and gives solution with the lowest value found in the objective function as required.

Chapter IV

Experimental Results and Comparisons

4.1 Introduction

For the experiment, RNA pseudoknotted sequences were taken from five datasets. The datasets are shown in Table 3. Parameter settings for our proposed method are given in Table 2. In the comparison of the experimental results, we have used the word CRO_RNA for our proposed work and other four algorithms Knotty, IPknot, SA, and TT2NE. In Tables 4, 6, 8, 11, and 12, we have shown the performance comparison of our method CRO_RNA without repair function and with repair function in terms of Sensitivity, PPV, and F-measure. In Tables 5, 7, and 9, we have shown the performance comparison of our method CRO_RNA without repair function and with repair function in terms of TP, FP, and FN. Table 10 shows the comparison of our method with Knotty and IPknot. Again, in Table 13, we have shown the comparison of CRO_RNA with SA and TT2NE. In Tables 14, 15, 16, and 17, we have shown the comparison for execution time of our algorithm with other mentioned algorithms above. The prediction accuracy is calculated by comparing the predicted structure with the known structure. Our algorithm was implemented on Lenovo personal laptop. Model number: G40-70 with Intel Core i3-4030U CPU @ 1.90GHz (4CPUs), 1.90 GHz, 4096 MB RAM and running on Ubuntu 16.04 LTS (64 bit). For the implementation, Python 3.6.2 programming language was used. We have taken the best results of 20 rounds for every sequence of the proposed method. The proposed method shows the better results for all the datasets than the other five mentioned algorithms. To evaluate the performance of our proposed method, we have used Sensitivity, PPV, and F-measure. **Sensitivity** is defined as the ratio of true positives (i.e., base pairs present in both the predicted structure and the true structure) to the total number of base pairs in the true structure. **PPV** is defined as the ratio of the true positives to the total number of base pairs (positive and negative) in the predicted structure. Sensitivity and PPV both indicate the accuracy of the algorithm of the base-pair prediction. The **F-measure** (F1 score or F score) is a measure of a test's accuracy and is defined as the weighted harmonic mean of the Sensitivity and PPV. Sensitivity, PPV, and F-measure are formulated as follows [6]:

$$Sensitivity = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (7)$$

$$PPV = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (8)$$

$$F\text{-measure} = \frac{2 * \text{Sensitivity} * \text{PPV}}{\text{Sensitivity} + \text{PPV}} \quad (9)$$

Where TP is the number of correctly predicted base pairs. FP is the number of incorrectly predicted base pairs and FN is the number of base pairs in the known structure that are not predicted.

4.2 Datasets

We have used several datasets of RNA secondary structure with pseudoknots to evaluate the performance of our algorithm. The first dataset is constructed from the same types of RNA sequences used in IPknot [7] called IP-pk168 dataset. This dataset contains 168 pseudoknotted structures from 16 categories of pseudoknots. The maximum length of sequence is 140. Another dataset is HK-PK which is compiled from RNA STRAND database [15] and is used in evaluating HotKnots V2.0 [24]. DK-PK 16 contains 16 pseudoknotted structures with strong experimental support of length from 34 to 377 [15]. To evaluate the performance and to show comparison between Simulated Annealing [14] and CRO_RNA, we have used a dataset that contains 10 pseudoknotted RNA sequence of length from 41 to 134 nucleotides from Pseudobase++ RNA database. Another dataset is a subset of CC06 [9]. We construct it from Pseudobase++ RNA database. It contains 10 RNA pseudoknotted sequence of length from 41 to 62 nucleotides.

Table 3. Datasets used in CRO_RNA

Sl.	Dataset	Number of Sequences	Length	Reference
1	PK-168	168	21-137	[7]
2	HK-PK	88	26-210	[24]
3	DK-PK 16	16	34-377	[15]
4	SA	10	41-134	[14]
5	CC06	10	41-62	[9]

4.3 Performance Comparison with existing algorithm

Table 4 shows the output of CRO_RNA with repair function and without repair function on PK-168 dataset in terms of Sensitivity, PPV, and F-measure. For 130 sequences out of 164, CRO_RNA with repair function performs better in terms of F-measure. The repair function has a great influence on the performance measure.

Table 4. Output of CRO_RNA tested on PK-168 [7] dataset in terms of Sensitivity, PPV, and F-measure.

Sl.	PKB No.	CRO_RNA without repair			CRO_RNA with repair		
		Sensitivity	PPV	F-measure	Sensitivity	PPV	F-measure
1	1	66.67	100	80	100.0	100.0	100.0
2	2	100	100	100	100.0	100.0	100.0
3	3	60	46.15	52.17	100.0	100.0	100.0
4	4	54.55	100	70.59	100.0	100.0	100.0
5	5	87.5	58.33	70	87.5	58.3	70.0
6	6	100	64.29	78.26	100.0	69.2	81.8
7	7	44.44	36.36	40	66.7	100.0	80.0
8	8	66.67	100	80	77.8	87.5	82.4
9	9	100	64.29	78.26	100.0	81.8	90.0
10	10	88.89	80	84.21	88.9	57.1	69.6
11	11	66.67	50	57.14	66.7	60.0	63.2
12	12	62.5	62.5	62.5	100.0	66.7	80.0
13	13	66.67	54.55	60	100.0	64.3	78.3
14	14	66.67	75	70.59	66.7	75.0	70.6
15	15	66.67	54.55	60	88.9	80.0	84.2
16	16	66.67	54.55	60	100.0	100.0	100.0
17	17	87.5	87.5	87.5	87.5	70.0	77.8
18	18	57.14	28.57	38.1	57.1	44.4	50.0
19	19	100	50	66.67	85.7	50.0	63.2
20	20	75	100	85.71	100.0	85.7	92.3
21	21	100	100	100	100.0	100.0	100.0
22	22	100	78.57	88	100.0	84.6	91.7
23	23	85.71	50	63.16	85.7	75.0	80.0
24	24	64.29	56.25	60	71.4	62.5	66.7
25	25	66.67	66.67	66.67	66.7	85.7	75.0
26	26	85.71	42.86	57.14	85.7	42.9	57.1
27	27	100	50	66.67	85.7	50.0	63.2
28	28	85.71	40	54.55	71.4	55.6	62.5
29	29	85.71	42.86	57.14	57.1	57.1	57.1
30	30	62.5	35.71	45.45	62.5	45.5	52.6
31	31	62.5	50	55.56	87.5	53.9	66.7
32	32	66.67	100	80	88.9	100.0	94.1
33	33	62.5	100	76.92	100.0	100.0	100.0
34	34	62.5	100	76.92	100.0	100.0	100.0
35	35	62.5	100	76.92	100.0	100.0	100.0
36	36	50	70	58.33	100.0	77.8	87.5
37	37	37.5	25	30	87.5	53.9	66.7
38	38	100	61.54	76.19	100.0	61.5	76.2

39	39	100	61.54	76.19	100.0	61.5	76.2
40	40	100	61.54	76.19	100.0	61.5	76.2
41	41	100	61.54	76.19	100.0	61.5	76.2
42	42	0	0	0	57.1	57.1	57.1
43	43	50	100	66.67	87.5	77.8	82.4
44	44	62.5	100	76.92	62.5	62.5	62.5
45	45	60	75	66.67	90.0	100.0	94.7
46	46	55.56	71.43	62.5	88.9	80.0	84.2
47	47	46.67	53.85	50	53.3	57.1	55.2
48	48	85.71	75	80	85.7	85.7	85.7
49	49	90.91	100	95.24	90.9	100.0	95.2
50	50	68.42	100	81.25	73.7	100.0	84.9
51	51	57.14	57.14	57.14	57.1	57.1	57.1
52	52	78.95	88.24	83.33	94.7	94.7	94.7
53	53	85.71	85.71	85.71	85.7	85.7	85.7
54	54	55.56	100	71.43	66.7	85.7	75.0
55	56	70	87.5	77.78	70.0	87.5	77.8
56	59	55.56	100	71.43	55.6	100.0	71.4
57	61	66.67	85.71	75	77.8	87.5	82.4
58	63	55.56	100	71.43	55.6	100.0	71.4
59	67	50	100	66.67	70.0	100.0	82.4
60	69	43.75	58.33	50	56.3	56.3	56.3
61	70	35.29	100	52.17	76.5	86.7	81.3
62	72	70.59	52.17	60	64.7	50.0	56.4
63	73	58.33	100	73.68	91.7	100.0	95.7
64	74	54.55	100	70.59	54.6	100.0	70.6
65	79	100	75	85.71	100.0	79.0	88.2
66	80	100	100	100	100.0	100.0	100.0
67	82	57.14	57.14	57.14	57.1	66.7	61.5
68	83	100	100	100	100.0	100.0	100.0
69	85	66.67	100	80	66.7	100.0	80.0
70	86	62.5	100	76.92	62.5	100.0	76.9
71	87	77.78	70	73.68	88.9	100.0	94.1
72	89	100	100	100	100.0	100.0	100.0
73	90	66.67	100	80	77.8	87.5	82.4
74	91	55.56	83.33	66.67	55.6	83.3	66.7
75	92	50	100	66.67	100.0	100.0	100.0
76	93	66.67	100	80	66.7	100.0	80.0
77	94	72.73	100	84.21	100.0	84.6	91.7
78	95	57.14	100	72.73	85.7	85.7	85.7
79	96	66.67	100	80	66.7	100.0	80.0
80	100	91.67	91.67	91.67	91.7	91.7	91.7
81	101	60	66.67	63.16	60.0	100.0	75.0
82	102	100	88.89	94.12	100.0	88.9	94.1
83	103	57.14	80	66.67	57.1	80.0	66.7

84	104	66.67	100	80	66.7	100.0	80.0
85	105	11.11	16.67	13.33	44.4	66.7	53.3
86	107	100	100	100	100.0	100.0	100.0
87	109	66.67	100	80	66.7	100.0	80.0
88	111	77.78	87.5	82.35	77.8	87.5	82.4
89	113	66.67	100	80	66.7	100.0	80.0
90	115	66.67	100	80	100.0	100.0	100.0
91	116	70	70	70	80.0	66.7	72.7
92	117	66.67	100	80	66.7	100.0	80.0
93	118	60	60	60	60.0	85.7	70.6
94	119	66.67	100	80	66.7	100.0	80.0
95	120	100	100	100	100.0	100.0	100.0
96	121	62.5	83.33	71.43	87.5	70.0	77.8
97	122	58.33	87.5	70	66.7	100.0	80.0
98	123	60	66.67	63.16	80.0	80.0	80.0
99	124	70	100	82.35	100.0	100.0	100.0
100	125	66.67	66.67	66.67	66.7	75.0	70.6
101	126	62.5	45.45	52.63	66.7	100.0	80.0
102	130	65.91	61.7	63.74	100.0	100.0	100.0
103	134	93.55	80.56	86.57	77.3	63.0	69.4
104	138	72.22	65	68.42	93.6	80.6	86.6
105	147	63.64	100	77.78	72.2	68.4	70.3
106	151	70	100	82.35	90.9	83.3	87.0
107	152	50	62.5	55.56	90.0	90.0	90.0
108	153	100	100	100	80.0	100.0	88.9
109	154	62.5	100	76.92	100.0	100.0	100.0
110	155	85.71	85.71	85.71	62.5	100.0	76.9
111	156	88.89	72.73	80	85.7	85.7	85.7
112	157	100	100	100	77.8	87.5	82.4
113	158	87.5	87.5	87.5	100.0	100.0	100.0
114	159	100	100	100	87.5	87.5	87.5
115	160	66.67	100	80	100.0	100.0	100.0
116	161	81.82	69.23	75	88.9	88.9	88.9
117	162	62.5	100	76.92	81.8	90.0	85.7
118	165	66.67	100	80	62.5	100.0	76.9
119	166	58.33	100	73.68	100.0	100.0	100.0
120	167	94.12	84.21	88.89	58.3	100.0	73.7
121	168	100	100	100	94.1	80.0	86.5
122	172	100	77.27	87.18	100.0	100.0	100.0
123	177	62.5	38.46	47.62	100.0	81.0	89.5
124	182	70	100	82.35	100.0	57.1	72.7
125	183	81.82	90	85.71	90.0	90.0	90.0
126	184	66.67	100	80	81.8	90.0	85.7
127	185	50	71.43	58.82	66.7	100.0	80.0
128	186	100	100	100	100.0	83.3	90.9

129	187	62.5	100	76.92	75.0	100.0	85.7
130	188	81.82	90	85.71	87.5	77.8	82.4
131	189	57.14	88.89	69.57	72.7	88.9	80.0
132	190	100	100	100	78.6	78.6	78.6
133	191	70	100	82.35	100.0	100.0	100.0
134	194	90.91	90.91	90.91	100.0	90.9	95.2
135	195	66.67	100	80	90.9	76.9	83.3
136	196	55.56	55.56	55.56	66.7	100.0	80.0
137	197	55.56	62.5	58.82	100.0	90.0	94.7
138	198	87.5	77.78	82.35	55.6	62.5	58.8
139	199	63.64	77.78	70	87.5	77.8	82.4
140	200	70	100	82.35	90.9	100.0	95.2
141	201	90.91	90.91	90.91	70.0	100.0	82.4
142	202	66.67	100	80	90.9	90.9	90.9
143	203	88.89	72.73	80	66.7	100.0	80.0
144	204	63.64	46.67	53.85	88.9	88.9	88.9
145	206	66.67	57.14	61.54	72.7	66.7	69.6
146	207	52.38	68.75	59.46	100.0	100.0	100.0
147	212	64.29	81.82	72	66.7	58.3	62.2
148	213	19.05	23.53	21.05	64.3	81.8	72.0
149	215	92.86	68.42	78.79	52.4	52.4	52.4
150	216	80	76.19	78.05	85.7	80.0	82.8
151	220	100	77.78	87.5	80.0	76.2	78.1
152	221	46.15	54.55	50	100.0	77.8	87.5
153	224	70	77.78	73.68	76.9	76.9	76.9
154	226	92.86	72.22	81.25	90.0	75.0	81.8
155	227	28.57	37.5	32.43	78.6	73.3	75.9
156	229	47.06	61.54	53.33	42.9	52.9	47.4
157	230	47.06	36.36	41.03	70.6	80.0	75.0
158	232	63.16	50	55.81	82.4	66.7	73.7
159	233	69.57	72.73	71.11	79.0	75.0	76.9
160	235	62.07	64.29	63.16	69.6	84.2	76.2
161	237	88	88	88	58.6	58.6	58.6
162	238	100	100	100	88.0	100.0	93.6
163	240	100	78.57	88	100.0	100.0	100.0
164	241	66.67	100	80	100.0	84.6	91.7
165	242	51.61	50	50.79	66.7	100.0	80.0
166	243	70.59	70.59	70.59	71.0	59.5	64.7
167	244	100	100	100	88.2	68.2	76.9
168	245	66.67	100	80	100.0	100.0	100.0
	Average	71.50	78.29	74.74	81.8	83.4	82.6

Table 5 shows the output of CRO_RNA with repair function and without repair function on PK-168 dataset in terms of TP, FP, and FN. For 140 sequences out of 164, TP increases and thus FN

decreases in CRO_RNA with repair function. The repair function has a great influence on the performance measure.

Table 5. Output of CRO_RNA tested on PK-168 [7] dataset in terms of TP, FP, and FN.

Sl.	PKB No.	CRO_RNA without repair			CRO_RNA with repair		
		TP	FP	FN	TP	FP	FN
1	1	6	0	3	9	0	0
2	2	9	0	0	9	0	0
3	3	6	7	4	10	0	0
4	4	6	0	5	11	0	0
5	5	7	5	1	7	5	1
6	6	9	5	0	9	4	0
7	7	4	7	5	6	0	3
8	8	6	0	3	7	1	2
9	9	9	5	0	9	2	0
10	10	8	2	1	8	6	1
11	11	6	6	3	6	4	3
12	12	5	3	3	8	4	0
13	13	6	5	3	9	5	0
14	14	6	2	3	6	2	3
15	15	6	5	3	8	2	1
16	16	6	5	3	9	0	0
17	17	7	1	1	7	3	1
18	18	4	10	3	4	5	3
19	19	7	7	0	6	6	1
20	20	9	0	3	12	2	0
21	21	10	0	0	10	0	0
22	22	11	3	0	11	2	0
23	23	6	6	1	6	2	1
24	24	9	7	5	10	6	4
25	25	6	3	3	6	1	3
26	26	6	8	1	6	8	1
27	27	7	7	0	6	6	1
28	28	6	9	1	5	4	2
29	29	6	8	1	4	3	3
30	30	5	9	3	5	6	3
31	31	5	5	3	7	6	1
32	32	6	0	3	8	0	1
33	33	5	0	3	8	0	0
34	34	5	0	3	8	0	0
35	35	5	0	3	8	0	0
36	36	7	3	7	14	4	0

37	37	3	9	5	7	6	1
38	38	8	5	0	8	5	0
39	39	8	5	0	8	5	0
40	40	8	5	0	8	5	0
41	41	8	5	0	8	5	0
42	42	0	4	7	4	3	3
43	43	4	0	4	7	2	1
44	44	5	0	3	5	3	3
45	45	6	2	4	9	0	1
46	46	5	2	4	8	2	1
47	47	7	6	8	8	6	7
48	48	12	4	2	12	2	2
49	49	10	0	1	10	0	1
50	50	13	0	6	14	0	5
51	51	8	6	6	8	6	6
52	52	15	2	4	18	1	1
53	53	6	1	1	6	1	1
54	54	5	0	4	6	1	3
55	56	7	1	3	7	1	3
56	59	5	0	4	5	0	4
57	61	6	1	3	7	1	2
58	63	5	0	4	5	0	4
59	67	5	0	5	7	0	3
60	69	7	5	9	9	7	7
61	70	6	0	11	13	2	4
62	72	12	11	5	11	11	6
63	73	7	0	5	11	0	1
64	74	6	0	5	6	0	5
65	79	15	5	0	15	4	0
66	80	12	0	0	12	0	0
67	82	4	3	3	4	2	3
68	83	9	0	0	9	0	0
69	85	6	0	3	6	0	3
70	86	5	0	3	5	0	3
71	87	7	3	2	8	0	1
72	89	12	0	0	12	0	0
73	90	6	0	3	7	1	2
74	91	5	1	4	5	1	4
75	92	5	0	5	10	0	0
76	93	6	0	3	6	0	3
77	94	8	0	3	11	2	0
78	95	4	0	3	6	1	1
79	96	6	0	3	6	0	3
80	100	11	1	1	11	1	1
81	101	6	3	4	6	0	4

82	102	8	1	0	8	1	0
83	103	4	1	3	4	1	3
84	104	6	0	3	6	0	3
85	105	1	5	8	4	2	5
86	107	12	0	0	12	0	0
87	109	6	0	3	6	0	3
88	111	7	1	2	7	1	2
89	113	6	0	3	6	0	3
90	115	6	0	3	9	0	0
91	116	7	3	3	8	4	2
92	117	6	0	3	6	0	3
93	118	6	4	4	6	1	4
94	119	6	0	3	6	0	3
95	120	12	0	0	12	0	0
96	121	5	1	3	7	3	1
97	122	7	1	5	8	0	4
98	123	6	3	4	8	2	2
99	124	7	0	3	10	0	0
100	125	6	3	3	6	2	3
101	126	5	6	3	6	0	3
102	130	29	18	15	8	0	0
103	134	29	7	2	34	20	10
104	138	13	7	5	29	7	2
105	147	7	0	4	13	6	5
106	151	7	0	3	10	2	1
107	152	5	3	5	9	1	1
108	153	10	0	0	8	0	2
109	154	5	0	3	10	0	0
110	155	6	1	1	5	0	3
111	156	8	3	1	6	1	1
112	157	9	0	0	7	1	2
113	158	7	1	1	9	0	0
114	159	10	0	0	7	1	1
115	160	6	0	3	10	0	0
116	161	9	4	2	8	1	1
117	162	5	0	3	9	1	2
118	165	6	0	3	5	0	3
119	166	7	0	5	9	0	0
120	167	32	6	2	7	0	5
121	168	12	0	0	32	8	2
122	172	17	5	0	12	0	0
123	177	5	8	3	17	4	0
124	182	7	0	3	8	6	0
125	183	9	1	2	9	1	1
126	184	6	0	3	9	1	2

127	185	5	2	5	6	0	3
128	186	8	0	0	10	2	0
129	187	5	0	3	6	0	2
130	188	9	1	2	7	2	1
131	189	8	1	6	8	1	3
132	190	39	0	0	11	3	3
133	191	7	0	3	39	0	0
134	194	10	1	1	10	1	0
135	195	6	0	3	10	3	1
136	196	5	4	4	6	0	3
137	197	5	3	4	9	1	0
138	198	7	2	1	5	3	4
139	199	7	2	4	7	2	1
140	200	7	0	3	10	0	1
141	201	10	1	1	7	0	3
142	202	6	0	3	10	1	1
143	203	8	3	1	6	0	3
144	204	7	8	4	8	1	1
145	206	8	6	4	8	4	3
146	207	11	5	10	12	0	0
147	212	9	2	5	14	10	7
148	213	4	13	17	9	2	5
149	215	13	6	1	11	10	10
150	216	16	5	4	12	3	2
151	220	14	4	0	16	5	4
152	221	6	5	7	14	4	0
153	224	14	4	6	10	3	3
154	226	13	5	1	18	6	2
155	227	6	10	15	11	4	3
156	229	8	5	9	9	8	12
157	230	8	14	9	12	3	5
158	232	12	12	7	14	7	3
159	233	16	6	7	15	5	4
160	235	18	10	11	16	3	7
161	237	22	3	3	17	12	12
162	238	8	0	0	22	0	3
163	240	11	3	0	8	0	0
164	241	8	0	4	11	2	0
165	242	16	16	15	8	0	4
166	243	12	5	5	22	15	9
167	244	11	0	0	15	7	2
168	245	6	0	3	11	0	0

Table 6 shows the output of CRO_RNA with repair function and without repair function on HK-PK dataset in terms of Sensitivity, PPV, and F-measure. For 81 sequences out of 88, CRO_RNA with repair function performs better in terms of F-measure.

Table 6. Output of CRO_RNA tested on HK-PK [15] dataset in terms of Sensitivity, PPV, and F-measure.

Sl.	Sequence	CRO_RNA without repair			CRO_RNA with repair		
		Sensitivity	PPV	F-measure	Sensitivity	PPV	F-measure
1	AKV-MuLV	46.67	58.33	51.85	66.67	58.82	62.50
2	BChV	50.00	100.00	66.67	87.50	100.00	93.33
3	BLV	66.67	100.00	80.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
4	BVDV_IRES	100.00	92.59	96.15	100.00	92.59	96.15
5	BWYV	55.56	100.00	71.43	88.89	100.00	94.12
6	BYDV-NY-RPV	55.56	71.43	62.50	88.89	80.00	84.21
7	BaEV	60.00	47.37	52.94	100.00	88.24	93.75
8	Bp_PK2	75.86	81.48	78.57	75.86	81.48	78.57
9	Bt_PrP	100.00	100.00	100.00	91.67	78.57	84.62
10	CABYV	50.00	66.67	57.14	75.00	75.00	75.00
11	CSFV_IRES	68.00	70.83	69.39	80.00	71.43	75.47
12	Cas-Br-E-MuLv	20.00	37.50	26.09	66.67	66.67	66.67
13	CoxB3	76.00	86.36	80.85	76.00	86.36	80.85
14	EIAV	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
15	Ec_PK1	90.91	100.00	95.24	90.91	100.00	95.24
16	Ec_PK4	78.95	93.75	85.71	94.74	94.74	94.74
17	Ec_S15	70.59	52.17	60.00	70.59	63.16	66.67
18	FIV	90.91	100.00	95.24	90.91	100.00	95.24
19	FeLV	21.43	42.86	28.57	50.00	58.33	53.85
20	GaLV	100.00	88.24	93.75	93.33	100.00	96.55
21	HCV_229E	91.67	84.62	88.00	95.83	100.00	97.87
22	HCV_Ires	75.00	65.22	69.77	90.00	90.00	90.00
23	HDV-It_g	90.62	85.29	87.88	90.62	85.29	87.88
24	HDV	70.00	95.45	80.77	86.67	86.67	86.67
25	HDV_anti	87.50	61.76	72.41	91.67	66.67	77.19
26	HIV-1-RT-1-1	100.00	84.62	91.67	100.00	100.00	100.00
27	HIV-1-RT-1-17	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
28	HIV-1-RT-1-3a	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

29	HIV-1-RT-1-6	57.14	100.00	72.73	57.14	100.00	72.73
30	HIV-1-RT-1-7	100.00	66.67	80.00	100.00	66.67	80.00
31	HIV-1-RT-1-8	85.71	75.00	80.00	85.71	75.00	80.00
32	HIV-1-RT-1-9b	60.00	100.00	75.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
33	HIV-1-RT-2-10	88.89	88.89	88.89	100.00	100.00	100.00
34	HIV-1-RT-2-11	62.50	100.00	76.92	62.50	100.00	76.92
35	HIV-1-RT-2-12	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
36	HIV-1-RT-2-1b	87.50	77.78	82.35	100.00	100.00	100.00
37	HIV-1-RT-2-2b	50.00	33.33	40.00	66.67	57.14	61.54
38	HIV-1-RT-2-3a	69.23	90.00	78.26	92.31	100.00	96.00
39	HIV-1-RT-2-4a	55.56	100.00	71.43	100.00	81.82	90.00
40	HIV-1-RT-2-5a	50.00	50.00	50.00	100.00	66.67	80.00
41	HIV-1-RT-2-6b	72.73	72.73	72.73	90.91	71.43	80.00
42	HIV-1-RT-2-7a	100.00	88.89	94.12	100.00	88.89	94.12
43	HIV-1-RT-2-9	62.50	71.43	66.67	62.50	71.43	66.67
44	HIVRT32	54.55	100.00	70.59	100.00	100.00	100.00
45	HIVRT322	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
46	HIVRT33	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
47	Hs_Prp	63.64	46.67	53.85	72.73	61.54	66.67
48	Hs_SRP_pkn	88.24	88.24	88.24	88.24	88.24	88.24
49	LP_PK1	50.00	100.00	66.67	70.00	100.00	82.35
50	MMTV	54.55	100.00	70.59	90.91	90.91	90.91
51	MMTV_vpk	54.55	100.00	70.59	54.55	100.00	70.59
52	MMTVgag-pro	50.00	100.00	66.67	91.67	91.67	91.67
53	Ni_VS	87.50	93.33	90.32	87.50	93.33	90.32
54	PDB_00716	72.73	72.73	72.73	81.82	75.00	78.26
55	PDB_00944	50.00	43.48	46.51	75.00	57.69	65.22
56	PDB_01009	75.00	60.00	66.67	70.00	51.85	59.57
57	PDB_01021	52.38	64.71	57.89	71.43	71.43	71.43
58	PDB_01023	59.09	68.42	63.41	63.64	60.87	62.22
59	PEMV	60.00	100.00	75.00	90.00	100.00	94.74
60	PLRV-S	50.00	100.00	66.67	87.50	100.00	93.33
61	PLRV-W	57.14	100.00	72.73	85.71	100.00	92.31

62	PRRSV-16244B	68.42	72.22	70.27	84.21	80.00	82.05
63	PRRSV-LV	89.47	89.47	89.47	89.47	94.44	91.89
64	RFA_00632	70.37	57.58	63.33	77.78	70.00	73.68
65	RFA_00636	85.71	68.57	76.19	89.29	69.44	78.12
66	SARS-CoV	84.62	75.86	80.00	92.31	85.71	88.89
67	SNV	85.71	75.00	80.00	78.57	61.11	68.75
68	SRV_1	100.00	91.67	95.65	100.00	91.67	95.65
69	T2_gene32	83.33	100.00	90.91	100.00	100.00	100.00
70	T4_gene32	54.55	100.00	70.59	54.55	100.00	70.59
71	TMR_00007	60.00	100.00	75.00	60.00	100.00	75.00
72	TMV-L	42.86	30.00	35.29	71.43	38.46	50.00
73	TMV.L	56.00	56.00	56.00	52.00	72.22	60.47
74	TYMV	88.00	75.86	81.48	80.00	83.33	81.63
75	Tt_LSU_P3P7	75.00	75.00	75.00	75.00	75.00	75.00
76	minimalIBV	94.12	84.21	88.89	94.12	84.21	88.89
77	pKA_A	100.00	85.71	92.31	100.00	85.71	92.31
78	satRPV	40.91	40.91	40.91	54.55	57.14	55.81
79	CRW_00611	75.00	76.60	75.79	75.00	80.00	77.42
80	CRW_00687	52.00	68.42	59.09	72.00	73.47	72.73
81	Coxsackie	71.43	78.95	75.00	61.90	89.66	73.24
82	Ec_alpha	79.17	50.00	61.29	75.00	51.43	61.02
83	TMR_00007	62.90	73.58	67.83	72.58	72.58	72.58
84	TMR_00009	80.00	71.64	75.59	75.00	72.58	73.77
85	TMR_00027_1	61.29	73.08	66.67	74.19	76.67	75.41
86	TMR_00049	46.88	34.88	40.00	59.38	65.52	62.30
87	TMR_00049_1	65.22	65.22	65.22	78.26	64.29	70.59
88	TMV.R	73.53	71.43	72.46	73.53	73.53	73.53
	Average	71.81	79.10	75.28	83.08	83.11	83.09

Table 7 shows the output of CRO_RNA with repair function and without repair function on HK-PK dataset in terms of TP, FP, and FN. For 79 sequences out of 88, TP increases and thus FN decreases in CRO_RNA with repair function.

Table 7. Output of CRO_RNA tested on HK-PK [15] dataset in terms of TP, FP, and FN.

Sl.	Sequence	CRO_RNA without repair			CRO_RNA with repair		
		TP	FP	FN	TP	FP	FN
1	AKV-MuLV	7	5	8	10	7	5
2	BChV	4	0	4	7	0	1
3	BLV	6	0	3	9	0	0
4	BVDV_IRES	25	2	0	25	2	0
5	BWYV	5	0	4	8	0	1
6	BYDV-NY-RPV	5	2	4	8	2	1
7	BaEV	9	10	6	15	2	0
8	Bp_PK2	22	5	7	22	5	7
9	Bt_PrP	12	0	0	11	3	1
10	CABYV	4	2	4	6	2	2
11	CSFV_IRES	17	7	8	20	8	5
12	Cas-Br-E-MuLv	3	5	12	10	5	5
13	CoxB3	19	3	6	19	3	6
14	EIAV	10	0	0	10	0	0
15	Ec_PK1	10	0	1	10	0	1
16	Ec_PK4	15	1	4	18	1	1
17	Ec_S15	12	11	5	12	7	5
18	FIV	10	0	1	10	0	1
19	FeLV	3	4	11	7	5	7
20	GaLV	15	2	0	14	0	1
21	HCV_229E	22	4	2	23	0	1
22	HCV_Ires	15	8	5	18	2	2
23	HDV-It_g	29	5	3	29	5	3
24	HDV	21	1	9	26	4	4
25	HDV_anti	21	13	3	22	11	2
26	HIV-1-RT-1-1	11	2	0	11	0	0
27	HIV-1-RT-1-17	9	0	0	9	0	0
28	HIV-1-RT-1-3a	9	0	0	9	0	0
29	HIV-1-RT-1-6	4	0	3	4	0	3
30	HIV-1-RT-1-7	6	3	0	6	3	0
31	HIV-1-RT-1-8	6	2	1	6	2	1
32	HIV-1-RT-1-9b	6	0	4	10	0	0
33	HIV-1-RT-2-10	8	1	1	9	0	0
34	HIV-1-RT-2-11	5	0	3	5	0	3
35	HIV-1-RT-2-12	8	0	0	8	0	0
36	HIV-1-RT-2-1b	7	2	1	8	0	0
37	HIV-1-RT-2-2b	3	6	3	4	3	2

38	HIV-1-RT-2-3a	9	1	4	12	0	1
39	HIV-1-RT-2-4a	5	0	4	9	2	0
40	HIV-1-RT-2-5a	5	5	5	10	5	0
41	HIV-1-RT-2-6b	8	3	3	10	4	1
42	HIV-1-RT-2-7a	8	1	0	8	1	0
43	HIV-1-RT-2-9	5	2	3	5	2	3
44	HIVRT32	6	0	5	11	0	0
45	HIVRT322	11	0	0	11	0	0
46	HIVRT33	11	0	0	11	0	0
47	Hs_Prp	7	8	4	8	5	3
48	Hs_SRP_pkn	15	2	2	15	2	2
49	LP_PK1	5	0	5	7	0	3
50	MMTV	6	0	5	10	1	1
51	MMTV_vpk	6	0	5	6	0	5
52	MMTVgag-pro	6	0	6	11	1	1
53	Ni_VS	14	1	2	14	1	2
54	PDB_00716	16	6	6	18	6	4
55	PDB_00944	10	13	10	15	11	5
56	PDB_01009	15	10	5	14	13	6
57	PDB_01021	11	6	10	15	6	6
58	PDB_01023	13	6	9	14	9	8
59	PEMV	6	0	4	9	0	1
60	PLRV-S	4	0	4	7	0	1
61	PLRV-W	4	0	3	6	0	1
62	PRRSV-16244B	13	5	6	16	4	3
63	PRRSV-LV	17	2	2	17	1	2
64	RFA_00632	19	14	8	21	9	6
65	RFA_00636	24	11	4	25	11	3
66	SARS-CoV	22	7	4	24	4	2
67	SNV	12	4	2	11	7	3
68	SRV_1	11	1	0	11	1	0
69	T2_gene32	10	0	2	12	0	0
70	T4_gene32	6	0	5	6	0	5
71	TMR_00007	6	0	4	6	0	4
72	TMV-L	3	7	4	5	8	2
73	TMV.L	14	11	11	13	5	12
74	TYMV	22	7	3	20	4	5
75	Tt_LSU_P3P7	15	5	5	15	5	5
76	minimalIBV	16	3	1	16	3	1
77	pKA_A	12	2	0	12	2	0
78	satRPV	9	13	13	12	9	10
79	CRW_00611	36	11	12	36	9	12
80	CRW_00687	26	12	24	36	13	14
81	Coxsackie	30	8	12	26	3	16

82	Ec_alpha	19	19	5	18	17	6
83	TMR_00007	39	14	23	45	17	17
84	TMR_00009	48	19	12	45	17	15
85	TMR_00027_1	19	7	12	23	7	8
86	TMR_00049	15	28	17	19	10	13
87	TMR_00049_1	15	8	8	18	10	5
88	TMV.R	25	10	9	25	9	9

Table 8 shows the output of CRO_RNA with repair function and without repair function on DK-PK dataset in terms of Sensitivity, PPV, and F-measure. For 14 sequences out of 16, CRO_RNA with repair function performs better in terms of F-measure.

Table 8. Output of CRO_RNA tested on DK-PK [15] dataset in terms of Sensitivity, PPV, and F-measure.

Sl.	Sequence	CRO_RNA without repair			CRO_RNA with repair		
		Sensitivity	PPV	F-measure	Sensitivity	PPV	F-measure
1	RF00010_RNAseP	51.79	58.59	54.98	49.11	59.14	53.66
2	RF00023_tmRNA	55.56	50.93	53.14	49.49	65.33	56.32
3	RF00025_Telomerase_Cil	66.07	57.81	61.67	57.14	69.57	62.75
4	RF00094_HDV	83.33	80.65	81.97	90.00	87.10	88.52
5	RF00114_S15	56.52	72.22	63.41	82.61	67.86	74.51
6	RF00162_SAMI	85.71	80	82.76	85.71	70.59	77.42
7	RF00165_BCV	81.82	81.82	81.82	86.36	90.48	88.37
8	RF00209_CSFV	40	43.24	41.56	43.75	45.45	44.59
9	RF00234_glmS	75.56	64.15	69.39	77.78	72.92	75.27
10	RF00290_BaMV	36.59	35.71	36.14	56.10	48.94	52.27

11	RF00458_IR ES_PSIV	66.67	63.64	65.12	65.08	77.36	70.69
12	RF00499_H PeV1	74.42	82.05	78.05	74.42	86.49	80.00
13	RF00507_S ARSCoV	79.17	67.86	73.08	87.50	80.77	84.00
14	RF00522_pr eQ1	100	100	100	100.0	100.0	100.0
15	RF01087_re pZ	75	69.77	72.29	75.00	88.24	81.08
16	RF01840_V MV	76.47	92.86	83.87	94.12	100.00	96.97
Average		69.04	68.83	68.93	73.39	75.64	74.50

Table 9 shows the output of CRO_RNA with repair function and without repair function on DK-PK 16 dataset in terms of TP, FP, and FN. For 8 sequences out of 16, TP increases and thus FN decreases in CRO_RNA with repair function. Both TP and FP decrease, but FP decreases at a rate more than TP while using repair function, and thus repair function gets the better output.

Table 9. Output of CRO_RNA tested on DK-PK [15] dataset in terms of TP, FP, and FN.

Sl.	Sequence	CRO_RNA without repair			CRO_RNA with repair		
		TP	FP	FN	TP	FP	FN
1	RF00010_RNaseP	58	41	54	55	38	57
2	RF00023_tmRNA	55	53	44	49	26	50
3	RF00025_Telomerase_Cil	37	27	19	32	14	24
4	RF00094_HDV	25	6	5	27	4	3
5	RF00114_S15	13	5	10	19	9	4
6	RF00162_SAMI	12	3	2	12	5	2
7	RF00165_BCV	18	4	4	19	2	3
8	RF00209_CSFV	32	42	48	35	42	45
9	RF00234_glmS	34	19	11	35	13	10
10	RF00290_BaMV	15	27	26	23	24	18
11	RF00458_IRES_PSIV	42	24	21	41	12	22
12	RF00499_HPeV1	32	7	11	32	5	11
13	RF00507_SARSCoV	19	9	5	21	5	3
14	RF00522_preQ1	9	0	0	9	0	0
15	RF01087_repZ	30	13	10	30	4	10
16	RF01840_VMV	13	1	4	16	0	1

Table 10 depicts that the average performance of CRO_RNA in terms of Sensitivity, PPV, and F-measure is higher than the other two methods except the sensitivity in DK-PK 16 dataset. The best outcomes are shown in bold text. Higher F-measure tends to higher performance. So, it can be concluded that CRO_RNA performs better than the other three methods in some respect.

Table 10. CRO_RNA is compared with IPknot [7] and Knotty [15] in terms of Average Sensitivity, Average PPV, and Average F-measure.

Sl.	Algorithm	Dataset	Sensitivity	PPV	F-measure
1	CRO_RNA	PK-168	81.8	83.4	82.6
2	Knotty		81.0	73.3	76.2
3	IPknot		80.6	75.1	77.0
4	CRO_RNA	HK-PK	83.1	83.1	83.1
5	Knotty		82.3	77.8	79.5
6	IPknot		58.7	64.6	60.5
7	CRO_RNA	DK-PK 16	73.4	75.6	74.5
8	Knotty		78.9	70.7	74.0
9	Ipknot		69.4	73.2	70.7

In Fig. 14, the graphs show the comparison of average performance measure between our proposed algorithm CRO_RNA with other existing (Knotty and IPknot) algorithms on PK-168, HK-PK, and DK-PK 16 datasets.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 14. The comparison of average performance measure in terms of Sensitivity, PPV, and F-measure between CRO_RNA and other algorithms (a) Knotty and IPknot on PK-168 dataset, (b) Knotty and IPknot on HK-PK dataset, (c) Knotty and IPknot on DK-PK 16 dataset.

Table 11 represents that the results of the proposed approach CRO_RNA with repair function are far better than without repair function. CRO_RNA with repair function gives output of 93.9, 86.1, and 89.8 respectively in term of average Sensitivity, PPV, and F-measure. Out of 10 sequences, CRO_RNA performs better in 6 sequences and performs equal in 3 sequences with repair function than without repair function in terms of F-measure.

Table 11. Output of CRO_RNA tested on a sub-dataset of CC06 [9] in terms of Sensitivity, PPV, and F-measure.

Sl.	Sequences	CRO_RNA without repair			CRO_RNA with Repair		
		Sensitivity	PPV	F-measure	Sensitivity	PPV	F-measure
1	BaEV	80	60	68.6	100	75	85.71
2	BChV	75	85.7	80	100	100	100
3	BLV	88.9	100	94.1	100	83.3	90.9
4	GaLV	100	71.4	83.3	100	79	88.2
5	IBV	88.9	84.2	86.5	94.4	94.4	94.4
6	MMTV	100	100	100	100	100	100
7	PEMV	90	81.8	85.7	90	81.8	85.7
8	SNV	85.7	66.7	75	85.71	85.71	85.71
9	SRV1	100	80	88.9	100	80	88.9
10	TYMV	69.2	69.2	69.2	69.2	81.8	75
Average		87.8	79.9	83.1	93.9	86.1	89.8

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 15. The comparison between without repair function and with repair function by CRO_RNA on CC06 dataset in terms of (a) Sensitivity, (b) PPV, and (c) F-measure.

Table 12 shows the output of CRO_RNA with repair function and without repair function on SA dataset in terms of Sensitivity, PPV, and F-measure. For 7 sequences out of 10, CRO_RNA with repair function performs better in terms of F-measure. For 2 sequences F-measure is decreased.

Table 12. Output of CRO_RNA on SA dataset in terms of Sensitivity, PPV, and F-measure.

Sl.	Sequences	CRO_RNA without repair			CRO_RNA with Repair		
		Sensitivity	PPV	F-measure	Sensitivity	PPV	F-measure
1	ALFV	86.67	68.42	76.47	100	89.47	94.44
2	AMV3	100	75	85.71	97.44	97.44	97.44
3	BaEV	92.86	92.86	92.86	93.33	82.35	87.5
4	BCRV1	100	100	100	100	100	100
5	BEV	100	72.73	84.21	100	100	100
6	CCMV3	89.74	72.92	80.46	62.22	65.12	63.64
7	Ec_PK3	84.21	88.89	86.49	94.74	94.74	94.74
8	RSV	68.89	62	65.26	82.05	76.19	79.01
9	SARS-CoV	100	62.96	77.27	96.15	96.15	96.15
10	VMV	80.77	75	77.78	100	87.5	93.33
Average		90.31	77.08	83.18	92.6	88.9	90.6

In Table 13, CRO_RNA is compared with Simulated Annealing (SA) [14], TT2NE [26], in terms of sensitivity, PPV, and F-measure. Simulated Annealing (SA) and CRO_RNA both have the average sensitivity of 92.6. However, in terms of PPV and F-measure CRO_RNA has the best performance. CRO_RNA gives the best accuracy of 88.9 in average PPV and 90.6 in terms of average F-measure. CRO_RNA performs better in 7 sequences out of 10 in terms of F-measure. In conclusion, it can be said that CRO_RNA performs the best in overall average accuracy measure than other methods.

Table 13. Comparison of CRO_RNA with Simulated Annealing (SA) [14] and TT2NE [26] in terms of Sensitivity, PPV and F-measure.

Sl.	Sequences	CRO	TT2NE	SA	CRO	TT2NE	SA	CRO	TT2NE	SA
		Sensitivity			PPV			F-measure		
1	ALFV	100	100	100	89.5	70.8	70.8	94.4	82.9	82.9
2	AMV3	97.4	74.4	89.7	97.4	72.5	100	97.4	73.4	94.6
3	BaEV	93.3	100	93.3	82.4	65.2	70	87.5	78.9	80
4	BCRV1	100	100	100	100	96.8	96.8	100	98.4	98.4
5	BEV	100	87.5	100	100	66.7	76.2	100	75.7	86.5
6	CCMV3	62.2	71.1	73.3	65.1	71.1	76.7	63.6	71.1	75
7	Ec_PK3	94.7	100	92.9	94.7	100	92.9	94.7	100	92.9
8	RSV	82.1	97.4	92.3	76.2	90.5	90	79	93.8	91.1
9	SARS-CoV	96.2	51.7	84.6	96.2	46.9	100	96.2	49.2	91.7
10	VMV	100	92.9	100	87.5	65	70	93.3	76.5	82.4
Average		92.6	87.5	92.6	88.9	74.6	84.3	90.6	80.5	87.6

Fig. 16 represents the graphs of the comparison of the proposed method (CRO_RNA) with TT2NE, and Simulated Annealing (SA) in terms of Sensitivity, PPV, and F-measure. From the graphs, it is proved that CRO_RNA outperforms other two methods.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 16. The graphs of the comparison of the proposed method (CRO_RNA) with TT2NE and Simulated Annealing (SA) in terms of (a) Sensitivity, (b) PPV, and (c) F-measure.

4.4 Execution Time Comparison

We have implemented Knotty [15] algorithm on PK-168, HK-PK, and DK-PK datasets to analyze and measure time efficiency of our proposed work CRO_RNA. After implementing both CRO_RNA and Knotty algorithm on the above mentioned datasets, it was concluded that the proposed work (CRO_RNA) is highly time efficient. CRO_RNA takes much less time than Knotty algorithm to predict RNA pseudoknotted structure. Knotty algorithm was implemented on Intel® Xeon® CPU E5-4657L v2 2.40GHz; for running jobs in parallel, the compute server was equipped with a total of 1.5TB available space. They implemented their algorithm using C++ language. The execution time comparisons between the proposed algorithm and Knotty algorithm on PK-168, HK-PK, and DK-PK datasets are shown in Table 14, 15, and 16 respectively. Here, the execution time is shown in seconds and the best results are bolded.

Table 14. Time comparison between CRO_RNA and Knotty on PK-168 dataset.

Sl.	PKB No	CRO_RNA (Sec.)	Knotty (Sec.)
1	1	0.57	0.875
2	2	1.01	1.222
3	3	1.05	1.688
4	4	0.57	1.303
5	5	1.28	0.53

6	6	1.77	0.575
7	7	0.83	0.587
8	8	0.41	0.459
9	9	1.65	0.574
10	10	2.09	0.477
11	11	1.96	0.548
12	12	0.73	0.436
13	13	1.56	0.585
14	14	0.53	0.474
15	15	1.06	0.532
16	16	1.06	0.57
17	17	1.28	0.529
18	18	1.48	0.399
19	19	1.23	0.405
20	20	3.81	0.421
21	21	1.44	0.517
22	22	1.29	0.241
23	23	0.79	0.379
24	24	2.67	0.914
25	25	1.58	0.063
26	26	2.5	0.342
27	27	2.08	0.399
28	28	1.01	0.341
29	29	2.67	0.338
30	30	1.66	0.519
31	31	2.31	0.485
32	32	1.44	0.372
33	33	0.52	0.47
34	34	0.72	0.463
35	35	1.32	0.472
36	36	2.21	0.894
37	37	1.27	0.482
38	38	2.35	0.485
39	39	2.39	0.486
40	40	1.49	0.441
41	41	2.22	0.479
42	42	0.52	0.367
43	43	0.4	0.386
44	44	0.34	0.397
45	45	0.79	0.52
46	46	0.59	0.409
47	47	2.73	3.732
48	48	2.41	4.042
49	49	0.59	0.145
50	50	3.14	3.151

51	51	1.62	0.986
52	52	2.59	1.894
53	53	0.27	0.041
54	54	0.49	0.043
55	56	0.53	0.06
56	59	0.12	0.063
57	61	0.83	0.059
58	63	0.12	0.047
59	67	0.3	0.152
60	69	2.19	3.951
61	70	0.27	2.2
62	72	2.14	6.537
63	73	0.47	0.231
64	74	0.22	0.11
65	79	3.84	4.007
66	80	1.09	1.187
67	82	0.54	0.074
68	83	0.73	0.071
69	85	0.23	0.071
70	86	0.2	0.065
71	87	0.8	0.2
72	89	1.29	0.223
73	90	0.53	0.084
74	91	0.54	0.228
75	92	0.09	0.094
76	93	0.13	0.062
77	94	0.49	1.3
78	95	0.09	0.063
79	96	0.39	0.057
80	100	0.77	0.185
81	101	0.69	0.084
82	102	0.3	0.079
83	103	0.48	0.074
84	104	0.27	0.078
85	105	1.73	0.175
86	107	1.17	1.595
87	109	0.58	0.062
88	111	0.58	0.064
89	113	0.08	0.056
90	115	0.19	0.056
91	116	0.97	0.218
92	117	0.44	0.058
93	118	0.46	0.212
94	119	0.58	0.058
95	120	0.68	0.318

96	121	0.21	0.082
97	122	0.46	0.171
98	123	0.46	0.079
99	124	0.1	0.114
100	125	0.4	0.067
101	126	2.8	0.107
102	130	1.15	0.452
103	134	8.01	250.419
104	138	1.94	38.419
105	147	5.16	1.725
106	151	1.17	0.203
107	152	0.36	0.087
108	153	0.8	0.217
109	154	0.4	0.076
110	155	0.14	0.05
111	156	1.13	0.05
112	157	0.59	0.077
113	158	0.8	0.129
114	159	0.35	0.081
115	160	0.82	0.175
116	161	0.64	0.096
117	162	0.64	0.276
118	165	0.76	0.05
119	166	0.12	0.055
120	167	0.72	0.267
121	168	3.66	62.244
122	172	2.73	0.443
123	177	4.21	7.915
124	182	2	0.567
125	183	0.15	0.094
126	184	0.88	0.167
127	185	0.44	0.133
128	186	0.58	0.112
129	187	0.3	0.062
130	188	0.44	0.105
131	189	0.58	1.065
132	190	1.75	1.065
133	191	5.39	0.129
134	194	0.84	0.16
135	195	0.42	0.059
136	196	0.23	0.123
137	197	0.95	0.177
138	198	0.43	0.051
139	199	0.48	0.128
140	200	0.57	0.123

141	201	0.49	0.244
142	202	0.79	0.057
143	203	0.11	0.12
144	204	0.95	0.994
145	206	3.41	0.969
146	207	3.28	0.915
147	212	2.7	0.931
148	213	2.05	0.921
149	215	5.95	0.907
150	216	2.46	0.891
151	220	6.16	0.881
152	221	2.45	0.75
153	224	1.82	0.721
154	226	2.7	0.793
155	227	0.73	0.782
156	229	2.98	1.199
157	230	1.02	1.211
158	232	2.61	4.235
159	233	7.43	9.11
160	235	5.73	13.147
161	237	2.75	38.652
162	238	1.56	17.44
163	240	0.35	0.475
164	241	1.32	0.236
165	242	2.1	0.241
166	243	6.81	120.527
167	244	4.75	2.391
168	245	0.77	0.265
Average		1.43	3.88

Table 14 shows that the proposed method CRO_RNA takes 1.43 seconds on average where Knotty performs that in 3.88 seconds. CRO_RNA takes much less time than knotty on PK-168 dataset.

Table 15. Time comparison between CRO_RNA and Knotty on HK-PK dataset.

Sl.	Sequence	CRO_RNA (Sec.)	Knotty (Sec.)
1	AKV-MuLV	4.22	1.41
2	BaEV	3.75	1.52
3	BChV	2.53	0.07
4	BLV	1.36	0.09
5	Bp_PK2	4.2	27.34
6	Bt_PrP	3.78	0.93

7	BVDV_IRES	4.61	10.15
8	BWYV	1.07	0.10
9	BYDV-NY-RPV	1.3	0.11
10	CABYV	1.26	0.08
11	Cas-Br-E-MuLv	2.09	1.33
12	CoxB3	4.63	9.13
13	CSFV_IRES	5.54	12.66
14	Ec_PK1	0.64	0.14
15	Ec_PK4	2.37	1.90
16	Ec_S15	3.28	6.67
17	EIAV	0.9	0.26
18	FeLV	2.39	1.35
19	FIV	0.49	0.27
20	GaLV	1.09	1.36
21	HCV_229E	2.69	4.02
22	HCV_Ires	3.81	2.78
23	HDV	1.22	24.82
24	HDV_anti	2.56	31.43
25	HDV-It_g	3.54	26.46
26	HIV-1-RT-1-1	2.57	0.35
27	HIV-1-RT-1-17	0.71	0.32
28	HIV-1-RT-1-3a	0.31	0.31
29	HIV-1-RT-1-6	2.74	0.32
30	HIV-1-RT-1-7	46.86	0.29
31	HIV-1-RT-1-8	3.08	0.39
32	HIV-1-RT-1-9b	1.19	0.37
33	HIV-1-RT-2-10	0.49	0.33
34	HIV-1-RT-2-11	0.82	0.38
35	HIV-1-RT-2-12	0.69	0.30
36	HIV-1-RT-2-1b	1.3	0.38
37	HIV-1-RT-2-2b	0.67	0.56
38	HIV-1-RT-2-3a	1.05	0.87
39	HIV-1-RT-2-4a	0.18	0.34
40	HIV-1-RT-2-5a	2.37	0.58
41	HIV-1-RT-2-6b	0.95	0.60
42	HIV-1-RT-2-7a	0.61	0.29
43	HIV-1-RT-2-9	0.63	0.24
44	HIVRT32	0.32	0.25
45	HIVRT322	0.58	0.25
46	HIVRT33	0.73	0.25
47	Hs_Prp	6.58	0.97
48	Hs_SRP_pkn	2.99	1.17
49	LP_PK1	0.47	0.13
50	minimalIBV	2.11	0.88
51	MMTV	0.74	0.22

52	MMTV_vpk	0.35	0.23
53	MMTVgag-pro	1.51	0.23
54	Ni_VS	2.07	0.66
55	PDB_00716	8.22	10.95
56	PDB_00944	3.62	5.41
57	PDB_01009	8.75	9.16
58	PDB_01021	5.73	6.81
59	PDB_01023	5.02	6.78
60	PEMV	1.2	0.09
61	pKA_A	1.09	0.34
62	PLRV-S	2.55	0.06
63	PLRV-W	0.39	0.09
64	PRRSV-16244B	5.62	3.38
65	PRRSV-LV	4.9	3.30
66	RFA_00632	2.99	31.32
67	RFA_00636	5.55	30.42
68	SARS-CoV	9.96	7.83
69	satRPV	4.88	9.62
70	SNV	3.76	1.46
71	SRV_1	1.37	0.35
72	T2_gene32	2.7	0.21
73	T4_gene32	1.1	0.10
74	TMR_00007	1.93	0.16
75	TMV.L	3.2	20.04
76	TMV-L	2.59	0.38
77	Tt_LSU_P3P7	2.4	5.56
78	TYMV	3.2	21.45
79	Coxsackie	2.81	88.42
80	CRW_00611	0.54	88.42
81	CRW_00687	1.94	524.83
82	Ec_alpha	3.69	428.91
83	TMR_00007	6.17	71.63
84	TMR_00009	7.89	1029.65
85	TMR_00027_1	3.43	53.66
86	TMR_00049	3.41	220.37
87	TMR_00049_1	1.71	222.57
88	TMV.R	6.49	46.83
	Average	3.20	35.56

Table 15 depicts that the proposed method CRO_RNA takes 3.20 seconds on average where Knotty takes 35.56 seconds which is so large. It also proves that CRO_RNA takes less time than other methods also for longer sequences.

Table 16. Time comparison between CRO_RNA and Knotty on DK-PK 16 dataset.

Sl.	Sequence	CRO_RNA (Sec.)	Knotty (Sec.)
1	RF00010_RNAseP	104.14	1998.77
2	RF00023_tmRNA	1.00	1901.22
3	RF00025_Telomerase_Cil	26.74	447.59
4	RF00094_HDV	1.51	24.39
5	RF00114_S15	0.35	10.66
6	RF00162_SAMI	0.23	31.24
7	RF00165_BCV	0.26	4.80
8	RF00209_CSFV	18.93	1375.90
9	RF00234_glmS	4.91	371.30
10	RF00290_BaMV	4.39	950.61
11	RF00458_IRES_PSIV	17.87	968.7
12	RF00499_HPeV1	10.12	97.55
13	RF00507_SARSCoV	2.67	18.09
14	RF00522_preQ1	0.06	0.21
15	RF01087_repZ	1.37	301.76
16	RF01840_VMV	0.18	6.60
	Average	12.17	566.85

From Table 16, we can say that CRO_RNA performs faster than Knotty for all sequences of DK-PK 16 dataset. CRO_RNA takes only 12.17 seconds on average where Knotty takes 566.85 seconds.

Table 17. Time comparison between CRO_RNA and Knotty on CC06 dataset.

Sl.	Sequence	CRO_RNA (Sec.)	Knotty (Sec.)
1	BaEV	0.41	4.53
2	BChV	0.03	0.49
3	BLV	0.02	0.90
4	GaLV	0.23	4.20
5	IBV	0.17	2.95
6	MMTV	2.71	1.21
7	PEMV	0.28	0.52
8	SNV	0.33	4.15
9	SRV1	0.08	1.61
10	TYMV	0.06	0.55
	Average	0.43	2.11

Table 18. Time comparison between CRO_RNA and Knotty on SA dataset.

Sl.	Sequence	CRO_RNA (Sec.)	Knotty (Sec.)
1	ALFV	3.12	13.89
2	AMV3	0.64	83.71
3	BaEV	1.09	4.45
4	BCRV1	1.78	42.97
5	BEV	0.51	3.54
6	CCMV3	2.23	202.81
7	Ec_PK3	0.17	1.88
8	RSV	1.42	160.37
9	Sars-CoV	0.89	18.32
10	VMV	0.19	6.69
	Average	1.20	53.86

Table 17 and 18 show that CRO_RNA needs less execution time than Knotty for all sequences of CC06 and SA datasets respectively. CRO_RNA takes 0.43 seconds for CC06 dataset and 1.20 seconds for SA. Where Knotty takes 2.11 and 53.86 seconds respectively.

Fig. 17, 18, and 19 represent Histograms for showing the execution time of Knotty algorithm and our proposed algorithm CRO_RNA on the PK-168, HK-PK, and DK-PK 16 datasets respectively.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 17. Histograms for showing the execution time of (a) CRO_RNA, (b) Knotty algorithm on the PK-168 dataset.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 18. Histograms for showing the execution time of (a) CRO_RNA, (b) Knotty algorithm on the HK-PK dataset.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 19. Histograms for showing the execution time of (a) CRO_RNA, (b) Knotty algorithm on the DK-PK 16 dataset.

4.5 Sample Input and Output

Table 19. Sample input of 10 sequences of arbitrary length.

Sl.	Sequence name	Sequence
1	PKB 194	UACGCUGUACAGUGCGUUAACUGUACA
2	PKB 120	UAGUGUUCGUGGAUAACACUUUAAUUAAGAUUCAUA
3	BChV	GGGAAAUGGACUGAGCGGCGCCGACCGCCAAACAACCGGCA
4	PKB 177	UGCUCUGAUGUCCCUCACCCACCCUGAAGA UCCAGGUGGGCGAGG GAACAGUCAGCGGGAUCACAGU
5	HDV	GGCCGGCATGGTCCCAGCCTCCTCGCTGGCGCCGGCTGGGCAACA UCC GAGGGGACCGUCCCCUCGGUAAUGGGCGAAUGGGACCCA
6	PKB 168	AUUGGUGAUUAUUUCCGCUUACUCCUGUGCGGAUGCAACAAUGUUUU GACAUUGAUCACUGAGUUUCAGACUGACUAACAGUCUGGGAUCCCCC AAGGGAGACCA
7	CRW_00687	CAUCCUCAAGGUGCUGGAAGUUACCUGCAAAGGUA AUUCAGCAGCC ACAUCUCCAUGUGGUUCACAGACUAAAUGAGGGUGGACCAAAUCCGC CAGGGUAUAGGUUUCAGAUUAAGUCGGCCUGAUGCGAACAACGUGUA CAGACUGCAGCG
8	TMR_00009	AGAGCUGCGGUUCGCUCUUA AAAACUGGUCGCAGAUUCAUAAUUGCCA ACGACAGCAAUACGCUCUCGCUGCUUAAGCAGUGAGCCUCUGCCCCG

		GAUUUGUCUGUGGAUCCGGAGCCGAAAGGGCGCGCGGAGGGUCAUGAA ACACGGAAUCGUGCGCAUUCUAGUCUGUGGGAUGCGCGCUAAAUUA AGCAGAA
9	RF00023 _tmRNA	GGGGCUGAUUCUGGAUUCGACGGGAUUUGCGAAACCCAAGGUGCAUG CCGAGGGGGCGGUUGGCCUCGUAAAAAGCCGCAAAAAUAGUCGCAA CGACGAAAACUACGCUUUAGCAGCUUAAUAACCUGCUUAGAGCCCUC UCUCCCUAGCCUCCGCUCUUAGGACGGGGAUCAAGAGAGGUCAAACCC AAAAGAGAUCGCGUGGAAGCCCUGCCUGGGGUUGAAGCGUAAAACU UAAUCAGGCUAGUUUGUAGUGGCGUGUCCGUCCGCAGCUGGCAAGC GAAUGUAAAGACUGACUAAGCAUGUAGUACCGAGGAUGUAGGAAUUU CGGACGCGGGUUCAACUCCCGCCAGCUCCACCA
10	RF00010 _RNAse P	GAAGCUGACCAGACAGUCGCCGCUUCGUCGUCGUCCUCUUCGGGGGAG ACGGGCGGAGGGGAGGAAAGUCCGGGCUCCAUAGGGGCAGGGUGCCAG GUAACGCCUGGGGGGGAAACCCACGACCAGUGCAACAGAGAGCAAAC CGCCGAUGGCCCGCGCAAGCGGGAUCAGGUAAGGGUGAAAGGGUGCG GUAAGAGCGCACCGCGCGGCUGGUAACAGUCCGUGGCACGGUAAACU CCACCCGGAGCAAGGCCAAAUAGGGGUUCAUAAGGUACGGCCCGUAC UGAACCCGGGUAGGCUGCUUGAGCCAGUGAGCGAUUGCUGGCCUAGA UGAAUGACUGUCCACGACAGAACCCGGCUUAUCGGUCAGUUUCACCU

Table 20. Sample output of the sequences with dot-parentheses structure and energy.

SI	Dot-parentheses structure	Energy	Length
1	.[[[.((((([)]...)))]))].	-16.07	28
2	.((((([[[[[]]]])))).....)]].	-18.39	36
3(((.[[[.])).....)]].	-19.45	41
4(((((((.[[[[[]]]]))..].....)))))]].	-12.02	70
5	.((((.....[[[[[.....]]]))..]..[[.(((((((.)])))))]...)]...)].....	-68.95	87
6	.(((((((.[[[[[]]]])).....((((([[]])))))))(((((((.....)))))))]...)]].	-36.73	105
7	(((((((.....((((([[[[[]]]])))))))(((((((.....))))))....[[[.]])))]...)]].	-129.61	153
8((((.....)))]..[[[.]]..[[[(((.....)))].....(((((((.)])))))]..]]].	-123.09	196
9	(((((((.....[[[.....[[[.....[[[[]]]]]))]])).....(((((((.....)))))))]...)]].	-246.99	363

Chapter V

Conclusions and Future Directions

5.1 Conclusions

RNA secondary structure prediction with pseudoknots is a significant challenge in Bioinformatics. RNA pseudoknots are found in almost all categories of RNAs. However, most previous works did not allow pseudoknots for its complex structure. This work presents the popular optimization problem of RNA secondary structure prediction with pseudoknots which is implemented using a metaheuristic algorithm called Chemical Reaction Optimization (CRO). The background and motivation describe the importance of solving the problem. The operators of CRO have been redesigned to solve the problem using CRO algorithm. In chapter II, we have reviewed some exact, metaheuristic, and heuristic algorithms which were used to predict RNA pseudoknotted structure. The hard tasks during the implementation of the problem were calculating the free energy of the structure by implementing three energy models and maintaining the accuracy of the predicted structure which depends on the value of TP (True base pairs), FP (False positive base pairs), and FN (False negative base pairs). The results of the RNA structure prediction with pseudoknots problem using CRO algorithm are compared with the related heuristic algorithm such as IPknot, Simulated Annealing (SA). We also compared CRO with an exact algorithm called Knotty. The results show that the proposed RNA structure prediction with pseudoknots problem using CRO algorithm performs very well and gives more stable structures. The additional repair function helps to predict RNA structure more accurately by removing the invalid structures from the resultant solution. CRO also predicted RNA pseudoknotted structure with less time than other algorithms.

5.2 Future Directions

RNA structure prediction with pseudoknots is the basis of RNA tertiary structure prediction. In future work, experimenting with the tertiary structure of RNA could be considered. Testing can be done with more short and long RNA pseudoknotted sequences to prove the prediction accuracy of this method.

Bibliography

- [1] Leontis NB, Westhof E, editors. RNA 3D Structure Analysis and Prediction. Volume 27. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg; 2012 [Nucleic Acids and Molecular Biology].
- [2] Tong, Kwok-Kit, Kwan-Yau Cheung, Kin-Hong Lee, and Kwong-Sak Leung. "GAKnot: RNA secondary structures prediction with pseudoknots using Genetic Algorithm." In Computational Intelligence in Bioinformatics and Computational Biology (CIBCB), 2013 IEEE Symposium on, pp. 136-142. IEEE, 2013.
- [3] El Fatmi, Abdelhakim, Arakil Chentoufi, M. Ali Bekri, Said Benhlime, and Mohamed Sabbane. "A heuristic algorithm for RNA secondary structure based on genetic algorithm." In 2017 Intelligent Systems and Computer Vision (ISCV), pp. 1-7. IEEE, 2017.
- [4] Akutsu, Tatsuya. "Dynamic programming algorithms for RNA secondary structure prediction with pseudoknots." Discrete Applied Mathematics 104, no. 1-3 (2000): 45-62.
- [5] Rivas, Elena, and Sean R. Eddy. "A dynamic programming algorithm for RNA structure prediction including pseudoknots1." Journal of molecular biology 285, no. 5 (1999): 2053-2068.
- [6] Sperschneider, Jana, and Amitava Datta. "DotKnot: pseudoknot prediction using the probability dot plot under a refined energy model." Nucleic acids research 38, no. 7 (2010): e103-e103.
- [7] Sato, Kengo, Yuki Kato, Michiaki Hamada, Tatsuya Akutsu, and Kiyoshi Asai. "IPknot: fast and accurate prediction of RNA secondary structures with pseudoknots using integer programming." Bioinformatics 27, no. 13 (2011): i85-i93.
- [8] Jeong, Samuel, Ming-Yang Kao, Tak-Wah Lam, Wing-Kin Sung, and Siu-Ming Yiu. "Predicting RNA secondary structures with arbitrary pseudoknots by maximizing the number of stacking pairs." Journal of Computational biology 10, no. 6 (2003): 981-995.
- [9] Cao, Song, and Shi-Jie Chen. "Predicting RNA pseudoknot folding thermodynamics." Nucleic acids research 34, no. 9 (2006): 2634-2652.
- [10] Lam, Albert YS, and Victor OK Li. "Chemical-reaction-inspired metaheuristic for optimization." IEEE transactions on evolutionary computation 14, no. 3 (2010): 381-399.
- [11] Saifullah, CM Khaled, and Md Rafiqul Islam. "Chemical reaction optimization for solving shortest common supersequence problem." Computational biology and chemistry 64 (2016): 82-93.
- [12] Chatterjee, Sajib, Resheta Ahmed Smrity, and Md Rafiqul Islam. "Protein structure prediction using chemical reaction optimization." In Computer and Information Technology (ICCIT), 2016 19th International Conference on, pp. 321-326. IEEE, 2016.
- [13] Kabir Rayhanul, and Rafiqul Islam. "Chemical reaction optimization for RNA structure prediction." Applied Intelligence (2018): 1-24.
- [14] Kai, Zhang, and Lv Yulin. "A Novel Efficient Simulated Annealing Algorithm for the RNA Secondary Structure Predicting with Pseudoknots." In International Conference on Intelligent Computing, pp. 365-370. Springer, Cham, 2018.
- [15] Jabbari, Hosna, Ian Wark, Carlo Montemagno, and Sebastian Will. "Knotty: Efficient and Accurate Prediction of Complex RNA Pseudoknot Structures." Bioinformatics 1 (2018): 8.
- [16] Chen, Jiunn-Liang, and Carol W. Greider. "Functional analysis of the pseudoknot structure in human telomerase RNA." Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences 102, no. 23 (2005): 8080-8085.
- [17] Neethling, Marais, and Andries Petrus Engelbrecht. "Determining RNA secondary structure using set-based particle swarm optimization." In Evolutionary Computation, 2006. CEC 2006. IEEE Congress on, pp. 1670-1677. IEEE, 2006.
- [18] Mathews, David H., Jeffrey Sabina, Michael Zuker, and Douglas H. Turner. "Expanded sequence dependence of thermodynamic parameters improves prediction of RNA secondary structure1." Journal of molecular biology 288, no. 5 (1999): 911-940.

- [19] Cao, Song, and Shi-Jie Chen. "Predicting structures and stabilities for H-type pseudoknots with interhelix loops." *RNA* (2009).
- [20] Zuker, Michael. "Mfold web server for nucleic acid folding and hybridization prediction." *Nucleic acids research* 31, no. 13 (2003): 3406-3415.
- [21] Liu, Zhendong, Daming Zhu, and Qionghai Dai. "Predicting Model and Algorithm in RNA Folding Structure Including Pseudoknots." *International Journal of Pattern Recognition and Artificial Intelligence* (2018): 1851005.
- [22] Andronescu, Mirela, Anne Condon, Douglas H. Turner, and David H. Mathews. "The determination of RNA folding nearest neighbor parameters." In *RNA Sequence, Structure, and Function: Computational and Bioinformatic Methods*, pp. 45-70. Humana Press, Totowa, NJ, 2014.
- [23] Kucharik, Marcel, Ivo L. Hofacker, Peter F. Stadler, and Jing Qin. "Basin Hopping Graph: a computational framework to characterize RNA folding landscapes." *Bioinformatics* 30, no. 14 (2014): 2009-2017.
- [24] Andronescu, Mirela S., Cristina Pop, and Anne E. Condon. "Improved free energy parameters for RNA pseudoknotted secondary structure prediction." *RNA* 16, no. 1 (2010): 26-42.
- [25] Mathews, David H., Jeffrey Sabina, Michael Zuker, and Douglas H. Turner. "Expanded sequence dependence of thermodynamic parameters improves prediction of RNA secondary structure1." *Journal of molecular biology* 288, no. 5 (1999): 911-940.
- [26] Bon, Michael, and Henri Orland. "TT2NE: a novel algorithm to predict RNA secondary structures with pseudoknots." *Nucleic Acids Research* 39, no. 14 (2011): e93-e93.
- [27] Bindewald, Eckart, Tanner Kluth, and Bruce A. Shapiro. "CyloFold: secondary structure prediction including pseudoknots." *Nucleic acids research* 38, no. suppl_2 (2010): W368-W372.
- [28] Reeder, Jens, and Robert Giegerich. "Design, implementation and evaluation of a practical pseudoknot folding algorithm based on thermodynamics." *BMC bioinformatics* 5, no. 1 (2004): 104.
- [29] Sperschneider, J. and Datta, A. (2008) KnotSeeker: heuristic pseudoknot detection in long RNA sequences. *RNA*, 14, 630–640.
- [30] Ren, Jihong, Baharak Rastegari, Anne Condon, and Holger H. Hoos. "HotKnots: heuristic prediction of RNA secondary structures including pseudoknots." *Rna* 11, no. 10 (2005): 1494-1504.
- [31] Fortnow L (2009) The status of the P versus NP problem. *Commun ACM* 52(9):78–86.
- [32] Lam AYS, Li VOK (2010) Chemical-reaction-inspired metaheuristic for optimization. *IEEE Trans Evol Comput* 14(3):381–399.
- [33] Lam, Albert YS, and Victor OK Li. "Chemical reaction optimization: A tutorial." *Memetic Computing* 4, no. 1 (2012): 3-17.
- [34] Chen, Xiang, Si-Min He, Dongbo Bu, Fa Zhang, Zhiyong Wang, Runsheng Chen, and Wen Gao. "FlexStem: improving predictions of RNA secondary structures with pseudoknots by reducing the search space." *Bioinformatics* 24, no. 18 (2008): 1994-2001.